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to AgroEcology

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Index

Executive Summary	viii
1. Introduction	1
2. Methodology.....	5
2.1 Territorial diagnosis	6
2.2 Definition of farm typologies.....	7
2.3 Identifying possible agroecological practices	8
2.3.1 Farmer workshop	8
2.3.2 Representative Board workshop.....	9
2.4 Living labs workshop to identify strategic options for agroecological transitions.....	10
3. Results	13
3.1 Ait Othmane-MA	13
3.1.1 Territorial diagnosis summary	13
3.1.2 Farm types	14
3.1.3 Farmer workshop	15
3.1.4 Representative Board workshop.....	17
3.1.5 Strategic options for AEPs by farm type	18
3.2 Laghouat -DZ.....	19
3.2.1 Territorial diagnosis	19
3.2.2 Farm types	20
3.2.3 Farmer workshop	21
3.2.4 Representative Board workshop.....	24
3.2.5 Strategic options for AEPs by farm type	25
3.3 Luxor/El Boghdady-EG	27
3.3.1 Territorial diagnosis	27
3.3.2 Farm types	27
3.3.3 Farmer workshop	28
3.3.4 Representative Board workshop.....	30
3.3.5 Strategic options for AEPs by farm type	30
3.4 PK-17-MR.....	32
3.4.1 Territorial diagnosis	32
3.4.2 Farm types	33
3.4.3 Farmer workshop	33
3.4.4 Representative Board workshop.....	35
3.4.5 Strategic options for AEPs by farm type	35
3.5 Siliana-TN.....	39

3.5.1 Territorial diagnosis	39
3.5.2 Farm types	40
3.5.3 Farmer workshop	41
3.5.4 Representative Board workshop.....	43
3.5.5 Strategic options for AEPs by farm type	43
3.6 Skoura M'Daz-MA	47
3.6.1 Territorial diagnosis	47
3.6.2 Farm types	47
3.6.3 Farmer workshop	48
3.6.4 Representative Board workshop.....	50
3.6.5 Strategic options for AEPs by farm type	51
3.7 Tizi Ouzou-DZ	53
3.7.1 Territorial diagnosis	53
3.7.2 Farm types	54
3.7.3 Farmer workshop	55
3.7.4 Representative Board workshop.....	57
3.7.5 Strategic options for AEPs by farm type	57
4. Discussion & Conclusion	62
4.1 Commonalities and differences among LLs regarding concerns	62
4.2 Commonalities and differences among LLs regarding AEPs.....	63
4.3 Methodology reflections – strategic options for agroecological transitions	64
4.4 Next steps	65
Bibliography.....	67

Glossary

Abbreviation	Full form
AEP	Agroecological practice
LL	Living Lab
RL	Replication lab
MAP	Medicinal and aromatic plants

Concept Category	Concept	Explanation
Living Lab methodology	NATAE Living Lab	Self-organized places of structural exchange between food system actors on the identification and testing of combinations of agroecological practices while working towards a joint vision for and implementation of an agroecological transition. A preliminary social and geographical delineation is provided in this document.
	Food system actors	Actors active in agricultural production (e.g. farmers) and/or the food value chain (e.g. consumers) and/or the formal institutions (e.g. local governments) that play a decisive role in agricultural and value chain activities.
	Stakeholder group	A group of LL actors with similar stakes and perspectives regarding the food system. Relevant stakeholder groups will be identified in each LL independently.
	LL-representative board	Group of about 10 persons that represent the different relevant stakeholder groups in regular meetings regarding the governance of the LL.
	LL-leader	NATAE partner organization that has been assigned with organizing and monitoring the LL process and reporting on its activities.
	LL-facilitator	An individual from the LL-leader organization or from a locally embedded organization which is hired by the LL-leader, who facilitates the Living Lab interactions. The LL-facilitator will be part of the LL representative board.
	Stakeholder activities	Data collection survey
Expert interviews		(Semi-)structured conversations with experts to gather data and insights that are mainly qualitative in nature. What is considered an expert depends on the specific topic that is studied. Experts can belong to a

Concept Category	Concept	Explanation
		specific stakeholder group or be actors outside the LL.
	Focus group discussion	Discussions with 5-10 representatives of a specific stakeholder group.
	Stakeholder workshop	Workshop for which members of all relevant stakeholder groups are invited to participate. Sometimes only specific stakeholders may be targeted (e.g. in farmer workshops)
	LL Representative Board workshop	Workshop for which only LL Representative Board members are invited
Typology framework	Agricultural system	Multiple farms operating in a similar context and (in)directly interacting with one another, e.g. via trading, managing common pool resources, other actors. It is part of the food system.
	Farm typology	The classification system to allocate farms to distinct farm types according to pre-defined criteria.
	Farm type	A cluster of farms sharing similar characteristics that, on average, are distinct from other farm types. In the context of NATAE, farm types include household characteristics.
	Representative farm household	A real farm whose characteristics are close (compared to other farms in the sample) to the average characteristics of a certain farm type.

Executive Summary

Agroecological transitions are essential for creating more sustainable, adaptable and resilient food systems. However, such transitions are notoriously difficult to foster. In this deliverable we present the work conducted within the Living Labs (LLs) of the NATAE project to identify strategic options for agroecological transitions in their local contexts. It is expected that these more targeted and nuanced options for agroecological transitions can facilitate the transition processes sought. To achieve this, each LL conducted a series of activities to identify the most suitable agroecological practices (AEPs) at farm and LL level for different farm types within their LLs. The process for the identification of strategic options for agroecological transitions, began with a territorial diagnosis (TD) of the LLs, which provided the contextual background to what AEPs are currently practiced and the socio-ecological factors that have moulded and continue to mould the agricultural systems of the LLs. This was complemented by two workshops with farmers and the LL Representative Board involving the core actors of the local food systems in the identification of the most pressing challenges and potential solutions of relevance. The development of the farm typologies per LL further enabled the LLs to take a more nuanced approach to understanding which AEPs at both farm and LL levels are suitable for which farm type, in effect creating a (strategic) toolbox of AEPs per farm type. The results of these steps are presented in detail per LL. In the discussion and conclusion, we assess the learnings from these methodological steps as well as the commonalities and differences among the LLs, drawing implications and conclusions from this work.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1. Introduction

Farming in North Africa is facing an unprecedented number of critical challenges. Over the past decades the region has been experiencing alarmingly high levels of land degradation with more than a quarter of all arable land currently now categorised as degraded (World Bank 2019, FAO 2015). Moreover, North Africa is considered a climate change hot spot which has led to high year-to-year precipitation variability causing severe draughts and heat waves (Schilling et al., 2020, Cook et al., 2016; Lelieveld et al., 2016). In addition to these environmental challenges, the region is also experiencing rapid demographic changes with large rural out migrations leaving rural areas with an ageing population and short of labour (Walther 2021). Rural regions in North Africa also have entrenched poverty rates, accounting for 60-70% of the region's poor people (FAO and IFAD 2007).

Agroecology has been posited as an important approach to address these challenges. Agroecological approaches tend to be less vulnerable to shocks to the market, extreme weather events, and pest outbreaks (Dagunga et al., 2023, Tittonell 2020). Moreover, agroecology helps to strengthen local economies, reducing poverty and improving livelihoods, creating a more equitable, socially just and sustainable food system (Altieri et al., 2012; Holt-Giménez & Altieri, 2013). However, agroecological transitions at scale remain notoriously difficult to achieve (Anderson et al. 2021).

Agroecological transitions are difficult to stimulate as farms are nested within broader socio-ecological systems. For example, the use of farm level practices (eg, the use of agroforestry, biopesticides, organic inputs) are not only dependent on a farmer's willingness or intentions, but also on a myriad of inter-related factors across scales such as a farmer's access to information and resources, value-chains, market demands, infrastructure etc. Moreover, these factors are influenced or controlled by multiple actors with different perspectives, interests, and relations. As such, to foster agroecological transitions it is necessary to create innovation systems that address the complex and multiscale nature of the socio-ecological system in which they are situated (Tittonell 2020).

This Deliverable provides an overview of the work conducted within NATAE to address this multiscale challenge, through the identification of strategic options for agroecological transitions. The term "strategic options" has been used to refer to the combination of agronomic and socio-economic practices at farm and LL level, that can together address several multiscale sustainability challenges in the food system.

Food systems provide multiple services, goods and benefits (outputs, food system services) to society such as the provision of food and bio-based resources (e.g. timber, fibre) but also contribute to the management of natural resources, such as water and biodiversity, and life quality in farming areas (Renting et al., 2009; Meuwissen et al., 2019). Sustainability of food systems is, thus, herein defined as their capacity to provide these services to present societies, without endangering this capacity for

future generations (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987). In this sense, sustainability challenges derive from agricultural management practices that affect the provision of these food system services to present and future societies. In NATAE, five main sustainability domains are addressed, namely, (i) environment and climate change; (ii) health and nutrition; (iii) society and culture; (iv) economy; and (v) governance (NATAE Deliverable D1.1). Following an understanding of agroecology as a multifunctional model of agriculture (Tiftonell, 2023, p. 22), agroecological practice combinations support the provision of multiple food system services, ultimately contributing to food system sustainability. Figure 1 illustrates the link between food system sustainability in the Living Labs with the provision of multiple services, goods and benefits to society across all NATAE sustainability domains.

Furthermore, the 'strategic options' presented in this document are considered strategic as they account for the diversity in farming practices by identifying farm types and targeting the different agroecological practices (AEPs) at both the farm and LL levels to these different farm types. The AEPs discussed in this deliverable will however be limited to the farm and LL scales as the work at higher scales (larger systems analyses and work on regional, national and international policies) is still being conducted. These scales of analysis will be integrated in a new Deliverable (D4.8) which is scheduled to be finalised in early 2026.

Figure 1: Conceptual diagram linking food system sustainability in the Living Labs with the provision of multiple services, goods and benefits to society across all NATAE sustainability domains (NATAE Deliverable D1.1).

To achieve the work set out above, the NATAE Work Package (WP) 4 project team in coordination with the LL leadership teams, their Representative Boards, and LL farmers have conducted a series of activities to identify the most suitable AEPs at farm and LL level for different farm types within their LLs. These activities included the development of a territorial diagnosis (TD) and farm typology; farmer and Representative Board workshops to identify and evaluate farm and LL level AEPs, and a workshop to identify the strategic options for agroecological transitions.

The Deliverable is organised along the following chapters:

- Chapter 2: provides an overview of the methodology for identifying the strategic options for agroecological transitions.
- Chapter 3: presents the results of the four methodological steps 1) Territorial Diagnosis, 2) Farm typology, 3) Farmer workshop and Representative Board workshop, and 4) workshop to identify the strategic options for agroecological transitions.
- Chapter 4 provides an overview of the commonalities and differences found among LLs in the execution of this the process to identify strategic options for agroecological transitions. It also reflects on the methodologies used and the next steps in the process as the LL endeavour to stimulate sustainable transitions to agroecology.

Chapter 2

Methodology

2. Methodology

Strategic options for agroecological transitions at farm and LL level are understood as combinations of agronomic and socio-economic practices at farm, landscape and value chain level targeted toward different farm types, that can together address several sustainability challenges in the food system. To identify these strategic combinations of AEPs, a series of activities were undertaken by the NATAE Work Package (WP) 4 project team in coordination with the LL leadership teams, their Representative Boards, and LL farmers under the auspices of each LL to generate a more contextualised understanding of the locations in which they operate, the heterogeneity of the farming systems present, and the possible AEPs at farm and LL level, that could contribute to agroecological transitions. These activities included 1) a territorial diagnosis, 2) the development of a farm typology, and 3) workshops with farmers and Representative Boards to identify agroecological practices and prominent challenges and opportunities at farm and LL level. Based on this information, in a project-level workshop, LL leadership teams were able to identify targeted AEPs at farm and LL level for different farming system types within each LL. A detailed methodology for the first three activities are already available in NATAE project documents:

- Territorial diagnosis: *T4.2 Guide méthodologique diagnostic d'un territoire rural: identification des pratiques agroécologiques et analyse de leurs conditions d'adoption.*
- Farming system typology: *D4.2 Farm household typologies in NATAE Living Labs.*
- Farmer and Representative Board workshops to identify agroecological practices and prominent challenges and opportunities at farm and LL level: *M5 On Living Lab roadmaps, agroecological practices, and scenario modelling.*

A schematic overview of how these different activities contributed to the identification of the strategic options for agroecological transitions is presented in Figure 2. The territorial diagnosis and the farm typology provided insight into both the socio-ecological context of the LL, the heterogeneity of farming systems, and thus possible entry points for agroecological transitions. This information was used by LL leaders to identify a long-list of possible farm level AEPs. These AEPs were then discussed in relation to farmer priority areas of concerns, and rated based on their perceived effect on these concerns as part of a farmer workshop. At the Representative Board workshop, stakeholders used the preceding background information and their expertise to identify critical bottlenecks to the scaling of farm level AEPs and possible solutions to address these bottlenecks at the LL level. At a project-level workshop, LL leaders then pieced together the outputs from these activities to create possible strategic options for agroecological transitions. The workshop output specifically identified which farm types would benefit from which farm level AEPs, and which LL level AEPs would support the scaling of these practices.

Figure 2: Schematic overview of the methodology to identify strategic options for agroecological transitions

An overview of these methodologies is outlined again below using text from the original documents in which they were presented. The project-level workshop where LL leaders identified targeted AEPs at farm and LL level for different farming system types within each LL is presented for the first time.

2.1 Territorial diagnosis

The territorial diagnosis was intended to contribute to the overall objective of taking stock of the situation of agroecology in the agricultural territories targeted by the NATAE project and its development prospects. The specific objectives of this diagnosis were to:

- 1) Identify agroecological practices in the territory studied;
- 2) Identify the factors (technical, economic, natural and others) that explain the existence of the AEPs the in agricultural production systems; and
- 3) Better understanding of the relationships between these factors and the rest of the components of the agricultural production system and its socioeconomic and natural environment.

In addition to identifying current agroecological practices, the diagnosis was therefore supposed to produce an analysis of the agricultural functioning model and its dynamics underway in the territory, allowing an understanding of the choices of stakeholders in terms of agroecological practices and their determinants. In this regard, understanding of the perception of local stakeholders, particularly farmers, in the local contexts, makes it easier to identify the barriers and levers to agroecological transitions (LL level AEPs) (Van der Ploeg et al. 2008).

The methodology of the territorial diagnoses comprised of four main steps (for more detailed information regarding these methodological steps, please refer to T4.2):

- Step 1 Conceptual and methodological framework – setting the limits of the system (object of study, its main dimensions, the key variables and the presumed relationships between them)
- Step 2 Characterization of the socio-economic and natural context
- Step 3 Characterization of agricultural production systems and their value chains
- Step 4 Characterization of agroecological practices and analysis of the conditions for their development

These steps were undertaken in an iterative way. The research was based on literature research (both grey and peer-reviewed literature), GIS analysis, and interviews with key stakeholders and farmers, and on field observations.

2.2 Definition of farm typologies

Agricultural regions are characterized by their socio-ecological conditions and their diversity of farms in terms of structure (e.g. farm size, crops grown) and functioning (e.g. intensity levels, market-orientation). This diversity influences how farmers react to changing conditions e.g. to extreme weather conditions, policy incentives or the introduction of alternative practices. A common methodology to deal with farm diversity is the development of a *farm typology* in which farms are classified into farm types (Alvarez et al., 2018). All farms within one farm type form a cluster of farms that share characteristics that (on average) distinguish them from other clusters.

Farm typologies are a valuable tool for rural development projects because they enable a more nuanced understanding of how rural development practitioners can identify practices at different scales that best address the specific needs and capacities of different farm types (Hammond et al., 2020). Moreover, by identifying groups with similar characteristics, development projects can prioritize activities where they are most likely to yield significant and sustainable results. For example,

extension services can design customized training modules for specific farm types, ensuring relevance and improved scaling potential.

A general recommendation for developing farm typologies is to use participatory and quantitative methods in complementary ways (Alvarez et al., 2018; Kuivanen et al., 2016). Participatory methods provide contextualisation of typologies, where quantitative methods ensure transparency and reproducibility (Kuivanen et al., 2016). Participatory methods also develop a realistic farm typology recognised and approved by local stakeholders, in contrast to being merely a tool for researchers (Alvarez et al., 2018).

Within the NATAE project, the preliminary method to create a farm typology in each of the LLs was undertaken by experts and LL leaders using the following steps:

- i) Definition of the objectives of the *farm typology* in consultation with local stakeholders,
- ii) Definition of the hypotheses associated with these objectives,
- iii) Definition of the *farm typology* criteria – ie, the most salient variables that distinguish among farm types (eg, farm practices, crop cultivated, livestock reared, farm size etc),
- iv) Data collection – through farm surveys, data needed to define the different criteria are collected,
- v) Statistical analysis (e.g. multivariate analysis or segmentation) to discriminate between the different types of farms, if possible based on the data collection method, and
- vi) Analysing the results of the typology in consultation with stakeholders in order to verify the initial hypotheses.

In some LLs the farm typology development evolved based using a more participatory approach, where the farm survey data was used to confirm and distinguish among farm types; while in other LLs, the farm survey data itself was used to first create the farm typology and the subsequently verified by LL leaders and experts.

2.3 Identifying possible agroecological practices

2.3.1 Farmer workshop

The aim of the Farmer workshop was to inform the potential suitability of AEPs according to farmers needs and the agroecological context in which they work. A number of AEPs were preliminarily selected by the LL leadership based on the insights generated from the territorial diagnosis and

interactions with experts. In the workshop, farmers and LL leaders discussed farmer concerns in relation to the set of pre-selected farm scale AEPs. To do so, a qualitative focus group discussion on the advantages and disadvantages of AEPs was held in each LL, followed by an individual semi-quantitative impact assessment. In this impact assessment, farmers were asked to assign importance weights (1 standing for 'not important', 2 for 'important' and 3 standing for 'very important') to different areas of concern regarding their decision making (see green infobox). In a second step, they were asked to evaluate the discussed AEPs regarding their expected effect (2 standing for 'strong positive effect', 1 for 'positive effect', 0 for 'no effect', -1 for 'negative effect' and -2 standing for 'strong negative effect') on the different areas of concern compared to the situation, in which the AEP is not practiced. In a multi-criteria assessment the importance weights and the effect scores were multiplied and combined into a practice score (per practice) and area of concern, in order to systematically compare practices. The results from the multi-criteria assessment were then fed-back to farmers, with the aim of facilitating the discussion around which AEPs should be tested experimentally and which to include in the modelling assessments.

Areas of concern

Water, Soil, Microclimate, Biodiversity, Pest and diseases, Animal welfare
Labour, Productivity, Consumption/processing, Costs, Revenue/income
Collective organization, Other (1-3 further options)

2.3.2 Representative Board workshop

Building upon the farmer workshop, the Representative Board workshop was designed to explore strategies to tackle challenges for the implementation of AEPs identified at farm scale through socio-political and organisational levers at the LL scale (LL AEPs, e.g., cooperatives, community seed banks, training etc.). These LL-level AEPs refer specifically to the activities that the actors within the LL can initiate with the potential support of additional actors close to the LL context. They do not include broader level levers such as national or international policies, which are addressed in another WP of the project. In the workshop, the Representative Board was first presented with the results of the farmer workshop, with a focus on the AEPs, the key concerns and the evaluation of the practices discussed. The Representative Board members then discussed barriers for the implementation of farm scale AEPs as identified by farmers. Similar implementation barriers across AEPs were grouped into 2-3 cross-cutting categories (e.g. marketing/value addition, access and management of resources/land, know-how etc.) and addressed in detail. With the help of *exploration trees* (Figure 2), as a tool to structure a group's knowledge (Quinio et al., 2022), the Representative Board members explored the question 'Which options are there to tackle the implementation barrier for AEPs at farm

scale?'. The metaphor of a tree was used setting the specific implementation barrier category at the tree basis and the question asked at the tree trunk. Individual tree branches were drawn for each option, i.e. LL scale AEPs, moving from broad ideas (large branches) to more specific actions (small branches). The options discussed focused on specific practices and interventions at LL scale. After the open exploration phase each Representative Board member individually indicated the 2-3 most important options from her/his point of view, from which a set of LL level AEPs were derived.

Figure 2: Example of two exploration trees drawn on flip charts to identify options to alleviate implementation barriers for AEP at farm scale in the Living Lab of Skoura M'Daz.

2.4 Living labs workshop to identify strategic options for agroecological transitions

The strategic options for agroecological transitions workshop aimed to piece together the information generated in the previous steps of the methodological process with the ultimate goal of mapping which farm level AEPs were most suitable for which farm types, and which LL level AEPs could support the process of scaling of these farm level AEPs. The mapping of these multiscale solutions from farm management (farm AEPs) to socio-political and organisational levers (LL level AEPs), considering the heterogeneity in farming approaches (farm typologies) based on an appreciation of the broader socio-ecological context (territorial diagnoses), can help define future pathways to agroecological transitions (Magrini et al. 2019, Tittonell 2023).

In the workshop, the LL leadership teams first reviewed a pre-selection of farm-level AEPs that corresponded with the farm type based on an analysis of the farm types and the AEPs (as developed by a project researcher). The list was verified and amended as required during a discussion paying particular attention to the farm type descriptions, as well as to the results of the farmer workshop.

Once this list was finalised, LL leaders were asked to identify the main barriers and levers (LL-level AEPs) to the scaling of the farm-level AEPs per farm type based on their own expertise, and the data and information generated by the Territorial Diagnosis and the Representative Board workshop. The resulting matrix provides an overview of the strategic options for agroecological transitions in the LL.

Chapter 3

Results

3. Results

The following sections present the results of the workshops and activities that were undertaken to identify the strategic options for agroecological transitions in the seven LLs. For each LL, a summary of the territorial diagnosis is presented followed by the farming system typology, the results of the Farmer workshop (AEP options at farm level, priority areas of concern, and the multi-criteria decision matrix), the Representative Board workshop (LL level activities for AE transitions). Based on this information, LL leaders have identified the strategic options for agroecological transitions by farming system type as presented in a table format.

3.1 Ait Othmane-MA

3.1.1 Territorial diagnosis summary

The Aït Othmane LL, a small agricultural area of 4.57 km² located in the extreme north-east of the commune of Mejjate, is made up of agricultural fields and scattered settlements. The area is bounded to the west by the Boufekrane wadi and to the east by a track near a provincial road. The northern part of the area ends at a trunk road and a motorway to the south. The Aït Othmane douar is located on the Saïs plain, with low-lying areas and a relatively flat topography.

Agricultural production is diversified, including cereals, onions and olive trees, influenced by tradition and self-consumption needs. Market gardening, leguminous crops and fruit production, adapted to local conditions, are also present. In recent years there has been a significant increase in the cultivation of aromatic crops (eg, mint, parsley, coriander) to meet urban consumer demand.

The marketing system is based on local sales through intermediaries. The majority of farmers in the LL find it difficult to sell directly to wholesalers, who prefer to deal with intermediaries with whom they have contracts. As a result, farmers often have to offer lower prices to remain competitive, which reduces their income.

Farmers are aware of the effects of climate change, such as rising temperatures and decreasing rainfall. In addition, water quality is reported to be deteriorating in the LL with an increase in salinity. Farmers are adapting to these environmental changes by adjusting their farming calendars and practices. Nevertheless, yields are decreasing, while diseases are increasing. Livestock systems are also changing with a reduction in cattle and sheep herds. Some livestock farmers are transitioning to poultry farming, which is more resilient to climate change and also meets a growing urban demand for eggs and beldi poultry (a local breed of chicken).

Farm incomes are falling, leading to migration to the towns or abroad and increased unemployment among young people. Women are particularly hard hit by the reduction in job opportunities in the

context of drought. To meet these challenges, farmers are adopting various adaptation strategies, but are encountering obstacles such as the high cost of techniques, the lack of subsidies and institutional and family changes.

To enhance soil fertility a few farmers leave part of the crop biomass cultivated in the field as green manure. Furthermore, while none of the farmers in the LL currently use mulching techniques, some farmers expressed an interest in learning the practice. Another practice, identified by farmers and stakeholders in the LL, to enhance both environmental and economic resilience was the integration of livestock to create mixed farming systems. Linking institutional partners with the LL farmers was also deemed of potential interest. For example, a partnership with the Ecole Nationale d'Agriculture (ENA) could enable the school to reduce its canteen waste by transforming it into compost to create organic fertiliser for the farmers. In exchange, ENA could become a customer and use produce from the LL farmers to supply the school's various refreshment areas and canteens.

3.1.2 Farm types

The main objective for elaborating the typology in this LL is the identification of existing agroecological practices and the promotion of new ones that are better adapted to the area specific conditions. With the assistance of local experts, the main criteria to differentiate the farms were selected: i) farm size, ii) market orientation, and iii) presence of livestock. From these, three farm types were defined (see Table 1)

Table 1: Summary of farm types identified in the LL of Ait Othman

Farm type	Description
Family farms	Small farms (<5 ha) based mainly on family labor, representing around 65% of farms in the Ait Othmane LL. This typology is based on crop diversification, combining market gardening, cereal production, legumes and aromatic plants. These farms practice crop rotation and integrate a viable livestock activity, contributing to the sustainability of the production system and improving family incomes.
Mixed livelihoods	Small (<5 ha), family farms that combine their farming activities with non-agricultural activities (salaried employment) to support themselves. To enhance income further they often rent part of their land to newcomers, who are particularly oriented towards profitability and the market. Main crops produced include cereals and vegetables.
Rented intensive farms	Intensive farms based on rented land (>5 ha), often originating from Mixed livelihood farm types (20% of village farms). These farmers aim to maximize the profitability of their rental investment, practicing intensive agriculture oriented towards production and marketing on local and regional level. Their system is based on monoculture often using an onion-mint-potatoes rotation, and relies heavily on hired labor recruited from the surrounding area.

3.1.3 Farmer workshop

3.1.3.1 Agroecological practices

During the Farmer workshop, five farm-level agroecological practices (AEPs) were discussed in detail. These AEPs were selected by the LL leadership based on the insights generated from the territorial diagnosis and at the Living Lab launch event. The first task that the farmers were asked to do was to identify the advantages and disadvantages of each of the AEPs. A summary of these discussions are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of the perceived advantages and disadvantages of different agroecological practices by farmers in the LL of Ait Othman

AEP	Advantages reported by farmers	Disadvantages reported by farmers
Drip irrigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less labour intensive than surface irrigation • Water-efficient, addressing concerns about water usage in arid or drought-prone regions • Enhances biodiversity, as it can help maintain beneficial species to the overall ecosystem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High investment costs associated with purchasing the necessary materials • Regular maintenance required to ensure the system functions properly, particularly in cases of blockages or wear and tear. • Labor demands for maintenance and regular monitoring
Use of manure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhances soil fertility and crop production. • Enhances soil health 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additional water to ensure proper integration into the soil, raising concerns about water sufficiency. • Potential for increased weed growth, • Inadequate irrigation after manure application may lead to crop diseases, • Labour-intensive • Amount of manure available is often insufficient to cover all crops, creating challenges related to crop yield and manure sufficiency.
Crop rotation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Positive impact on soil health, as it allows the soil to rest and recover between crop cycles. • Contributes to improved productivity, • Enhances the quality of produce, with farmers emphasizing its role in improving the taste of the harvest. • Diversification of revenue streams, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop rotation is labour-intensive
Crop associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhances soil fertility • Promotes biodiversity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suitable crops for association are currently unavailable • Crop associations are not currently practiced / lack of knowledge

AEP	Advantages reported by farmers	Disadvantages reported by farmers
Use of tree pruning residues for mulching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Retain water in the soil, contributing to soil moisture as well as fertility. Suppresses weed growth, reducing competition for resources and benefiting crops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can lead to an increase in soil-dwelling insects, potentially harming crop health Labor-intensive, requiring significant effort for pruning, transportation, and shredding of residues. Investment costs for machinery

3.1.3.2 Priority areas of concern

After reviewing the advantages and disadvantages of the AEPs, farmers were then asked to rate the importance of a pre-set list of areas of concern to them, which could be expanded based on discussions with the farmers. Farmers rated each area of concern on a scale of 0-3 generating an importance score.

According to the responses by the farmers (see Table 3 for an overview of the importance scores), the most important areas of concern included:

- Water availability and efficiency
- Soil fertility and health
- Revenue and income
- Productivity
- Pests and disease
- Labour availability and labour intensity of practices
- Consumption and processing possibilities
- Investment costs
- Animal welfare

Issues related to micro-climates and biodiversity were not rated as particularly important areas of concern by farmers.

3.1.3.3 Multi-criteria decision matrix

The final step in the farmer workshop was for the farmers to rate the AEPs as regard their effect on the list of priority areas of concern. The summary of these responses is presented in Table 3.

It is noteworthy that farmers rated the use of manure to be strongly negatively associated with areas of concern of water and pests and diseases, and also relatively labour intensive, suggesting that farmers perceived this AEP to exacerbate these areas of concern. Drip irrigation and mulching with tree pruning residues were also negatively associated with the area of concern of costs (ie, the practice was perceived as costly). Overall, each of the AEPs is perceived to require additional labour (except for the AEP of crop associations).

On the other hand, the AEPs of crop rotation and crop associations were perceived by farmers to score particularly well for the areas of concern related to soil health, income, and productivity. Crop rotation also scored highest in the area of concern related to consumption/processing. Drip irrigation scored positively with regard to water resources, soil health, revenue/income, productivity, pests and diseases, and consumption/processing. The use of manure scored highly with regard to the areas of concern of soil health and productivity, while mulching with tree pruning residues scored highly with regard to water and soil health. All AEPs scored positively on the area of concern related to soil.

Table 3: Multi-criteria decision matrix presenting the perceived effects of different agroecological practices on different areas of concern in the LL of Ait Othman

Area of concern	Drip irrigation	Use of manure	Crop rotation	Crop associations	Mulching with tree pruning residues	Importance Score
Water	6.00	-6.00	0.00	0.00	6.00	3
Soil	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	3
Revenue/income	3.00	3.00	6.00	6.00	3.00	3
Productivity	3.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	0.00	3
Pests and diseases	6.00	-6.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3
Microclimate	1.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1
Labour	-3.00	-3.00	-3.00	0.00	-3.00	3
Costs	-6.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-6.00	3
Consumption/processing	3.00	3.00	6.00	3.00	0.00	3
Biodiversity	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	-1.00	1
Animal welfare	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3
Overall practice score	19	4	26	26	9	-

3.1.4 Representative Board workshop

The Representative Board workshop was still not finalised by the time of writing, instead experts and the LL leadership were asked to identify solutions at the LL scale to alleviate barriers for the implementation of farm scale agroecological practices as discussed during the farmer workshop. Options discussed included the establishment of a cooperative to facilitate the access to subsidies for farm inputs, access and development of common infrastructure, and common marketing opportunities. In addition, it was proposed that trainings on crop associations, manure management

and composting (eg, with shredder/mulching) should be undertaken, and rainwater harvesting through the installation of common reservoirs (supplementing current water sources) could be explored through the development of a water management association.

3.1.5 Strategic options for AEPs by farm type

In a joint workshop with all LL leads, the leadership team from each LL identified which AEPs were most suitable for which farm type based on the detailed characterisation of the farm types and the results of the territorial diagnosis, and farmer and Representative Board workshops (Table 4).

All five farm level AEPs were deemed to be suitable for the mixed livelihood and rented intensive farm types. On the other hand, for the family farm types, all AEPs were deemed suitable except for crop rotations as this practice, which while very suitable, was already ubiquitous in their cropping practices and therefore not a practice that needed to be stimulated.

While cost was evaluated as an important concern for the use of drip irrigation and mulching tree pruning residues, it is likely that this is more of a barrier for the family farm and mixed livelihood types due to their lower income from farm activities. To address this barrier, the creation of a cooperative could help in providing access to credit and cheaper infrastructure costs. The development of common water infrastructure to enhance access to water was also deemed an important LL level AEP to facilitate the use of drip irrigation for all farm types.

Training for all farm types on crop associations was perceived to be important for the scaling of this farm level AEP. The same was true for crop rotations for mixed livelihood farm and rented intensive farm types. The use of manure was related to concerns of its perceived negative effect of water availability and the presence of pests and diseases. It is therefore proposed that training and demonstration plots could be used to explore these concerns further and provide evidence to farmers regarding their potential benefits.

Table 4: Summary of strategic farm and LL level AEP options by farm type in the LL of Ait Othmane

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
Family farms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drip irrigation (for farmers currently not using drip irrigation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cooperative establishment Common water infrastructure (water harvesting reservoirs)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of manure (dependent on availability) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and demonstration plots
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crop associations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on crop associations

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mulching/composting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cooperative establishment Training and demonstration plots
Mixed livelihoods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drip irrigation (for farmers currently not using drip irrigation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cooperative establishment Common water infrastructure (water harvesting reservoirs)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of manure (dependent on availability) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and demonstration plots
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crop rotation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on crop rotations
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crop associations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on crop associations
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mulching/composting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cooperative establishment Training and demonstration plots
Rented intensive farms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Drip irrigation (for farmers currently not using drip irrigation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Common water infrastructure (water harvesting reservoirs)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of manure (dependent on availability) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and demonstration plots
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crop rotation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on crop rotations
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crop associations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on crop associations
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mulching/composting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cooperative establishment Training and demonstration plots

3.2 Laghouat -DZ

3.2.1 Territorial diagnosis

Located in the south of Algeria, the Wilaya of Laghouat lies on the northern edge of the Sahara and covers an area of 25,052 km². It is bordered to the north and north-east by Djelfa, to the north-west by Tiaret, to the south by Ghardaïa and to the west by El Bayadh. It has an arid bioclimatic zone with an average annual rainfall of 154 mm. Temperatures can range from 3°C in the winter to a monthly average of over 33°C in July.

The Wilaya of Laghouat is mainly agropastoral, with a sheep population of over 1.9 million (88% of total livestock in the area), followed by goats 11%, cattle 1%, and a small number of horses and camels. Sheep farming is semi-extensive and has undergone major changes since the recurrence of drought, over-exploitation of steppe grazing lands, illegal ploughing and the introduction of state

support for livestock feed (barley for consumption and bran). In terms of crop production, 40% of the utilised agricultural area (UAA) is dominated by cereal crops. Laghouat has seen considerable development in market gardening over the past decades, with 15% of the UAA used for potato mainly grown in the northern agroclimatic zone of the wilaya. Fruit trees account for 8% of the UAA and oases for 0.34%, located mainly in the communes of Laghouat and El Assafia. Seventy per cent of farms have less than 5 ha of land.

In the area of water and soil management, the adoption of agroecological practices is widespread in the LL. This includes rational management of water resources, improved irrigation practices, staggered cultivation, and the use of organic amendments. Other agroecological farming techniques include crop rotations, integrated crop-livestock farming, and the use of wind breaks. Farmers often use organic inputs to combat pests and diseases and employ manual weeding techniques. With regard to livestock production, the protection of local breeds is promoted and seasonal transhumance for sheep is practiced. Adding value to agricultural produce and its by-products plays a crucial role in the region, and is very often carried out by women. The co-creation and sharing of knowledge, although infrequent and restricted to a small group, is promoted through the exchange of experiences, thereby strengthening the dissemination and adoption of agroecological practices.

Access to resources and markets pose important challenges of the LL. There is also a lack of critical infrastructure or equipment that can facilitate more efficient resource use, such as irrigation systems, composting units, recycling and production units. There is a perception that farmers need to improve their capacities in risk management and the use of some techniques that can help address some of the core challenges facing the farmers of the LL. Coordination and collaboration can be used to help change mind sets.

3.2.2 Farm types

An initial typology was proposed, based on expert knowledge and was defined following two workshops with the representative board. The data collected from the household questionnaire was used to refine and help further characterise the farm types. A validation workshop took place with experts from the LL. The main criteria to differentiate the farms included: i) number of animals and dependence on farm revenue from livestock; 2) share of market garden area of farm; 3) proportion of integration of arboriculture into farm; 4) presence of multiple production systems on farm. From these criteria, four farm types were defined as summarised in Table 5.

Table 5: Summary of farm types identified in the LL of Laghouat

Farm type	Description
Livestock	Different sized livestock farmers, rearing predominantly sheep and cattle, but also goats, horses, and camels. Farms usually own more than 50 heads of livestock. Livestock production is market oriented with both meat and dairy sold to local markets. The farms are medium to large and often cultivate crops both for forage and for sale to market (accounting for 50% of their land). Farms also often integrate trees and a small proportion practice intercropping. Off-farm income is rare.
Date palms and arboriculture	Small farms with less than 2 ha of fruit trees (date palm, olive, fig, and fruit production). Off-farm activities is ubiquitous among these farm types (either permanent or casual employment). Farmers are younger than other farm types. Intercropping is often practiced (sometimes with vegetable for self-consumption). Exceptionally farms also own livestock.
Diversified	Vary in size but all have field crops (cereals) and trees. Some livestock can be reared and some market gardening also takes place but these production systems account for a low share of income. When farmers have smaller plots of land, market gardening becomes a more important source of income.
Market gardeners	Market gardening accounts for the majority of their land and is the main source of income. Off-farm activities are rare. Usually do not own large livestock. Date palms are often cultivated.

3.2.3 Farmer workshop

3.2.3.1 Agroecological practices

During the Farmer workshop, six farm-level agroecological practices (AEPs) were discussed in detail. These AEPs were selected by the LL leadership based on the insights generated from the territorial diagnosis and in consultation with experts in the region. The first task that the farmers were asked to do was to identify the advantages and disadvantages of each of the AEPs. A summary of these discussions is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Summary of the perceived advantages and disadvantages of different agroecological practices by farmers in the LL of Laghouat

AEP	Advantages reported by farmers	Disadvantages reported by farmers
Composting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improves soil moisture Improves soil structure and fertility, source of humus, formation of organo-mineral complex, ion fixer Promotes microbial activity Free from diseases and weeds Healthy product Natural product, reduction and recycling of residues and waste, clean operation, reduce the use of chemicals Easy to use and ready to use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slow preparation time (traditional), lack of grinding equipment Lack of raw material, Demand for labour Lack of awareness of crop needs

AEP	Advantages reported by farmers	Disadvantages reported by farmers
Improved irrigation system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Optimization of water use, performance in the irrigation process • Prevents overwatering and soil leaching • Time control of irrigation, time saving • Labour saving • Robust, low maintenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of knowledge of the product and its use
Integration of prickly pear trees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No additional water requirements • No additional space requirements • Drought resistant • Enriches biodiversity, and reduces crop damage by providing a food source for beneficial birds (nightingales) • Windbreak and protection of cultivated plots against animals • It is a livestock feed and is very popular with dromedaries. • Not labour intensive • Good economic returns • Edible and transformable fruits • Low costs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitive to frost • Difficult to harvest • Lack of knowledge of its value and benefits
Date pollinator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficient and easy to use • Efficient use of pollen • Lower labour requirements • Increased income 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of equipment
Natural pesticides (Nettle porridge)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production improves biodiversity • Savings in the purchase of phytosanitary products • Reduces processing costs • Healthy and natural product • Diversity of uses (nematodes and other pests) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires many applications • Difficult recipe to make, requires training and mastery of the process • Lack of raw plant material, nettle poorly available
Value addition processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity of raw materials (bovine, caprine, ovine and camel) • Creation of family units • Diversity of cheese and dairy products • Family consumption, use of milk at all stages • Improved income 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of equipment • Lack of collection and processing unit • Unavailable and expensive inputs (rennet and ferments) • Lack of training

3.2.3.2 Priority areas of concern

After reviewing the advantages and disadvantages of the AEPs farmers were then asked to rate the importance of a pre-set list of areas of concern to them, which could be expanded based on discussions with the farmers. Farmers rated each area of concern on a scale of 0-3 generating an importance score.

The most important concerns identified by the farmers were (see table 7 for an overview of the importance scores):

- soil health,
- water resources, and
- productivity.

Farmers highlighted the difficulties related to financing the investments needed to implement agroecological practices, particularly in terms of equipment, infrastructure and training. They highlighted the obstacles related to working together, stressing the need to strengthen cooperation and coordination between stakeholders to pool resources and skills. Farmers also expressed concern about climate change, particularly recurring droughts, which threaten the viability and sustainability of their agricultural activities.

3.2.3.3 Multi-criteria decision matrix

The final step in the farmer workshop was for the farmers to rate the AEPs as regard their effect on the list of priority areas of concern. The summary of these responses is presented in Table 7.

It was noteworthy that the farmers perceived no negative trade-offs as a result of the use of the proposed AEPs, although in many instances the AEPs were perceived to have little or no effect on some of the areas of concern. The date pollinator, for example, was perceived to have no or very little effect on water, soil health, biodiversity, or animal welfare; while cheese making was perceived to have little or no effect on soil health, micro-climate, biodiversity, or pests and diseases.

Composting and improved irrigation were perceived to have a positive impact especially on water, soil health, productivity and revenue/income. Wind breaks on the other were not perceived to have as high a positive impact on soil and water as composting and improved irrigation, but was expected to improve the microclimate and enhance biodiversity more. Natural pesticides highest scores were related to their role in enhancing biodiversity and decreasing pests and diseases, while also improving production and revenues. The date pollinator was perceived to enhance productivity and revenue as well; as was value added processing, which was also expected to improve collective organisation.

Table 7: Multi-criteria decision matrix presenting the perceived effects of different agroecological practices on different areas of concern in the LL of Laghouat

Area of concern	Composting	Improved irrigation	Wind breaks (prickly pear)	Date pollinator	Natural pesticides	Value added processing	Importance score
Water	3.65	4.78	2.84	0.85	0.61	1.40	2.53
Soil	5.14	3.08	0.95	0.00	1.15	0.32	2.58

Area of concern	Composting	Improved irrigation	Wind breaks (prickly pear)	Date pollinator	Natural pesticides	Value added processing	Importance score
Microclimate	1.20	0.29	3.13	1.44	1.91	0.00	2.14
Biodiversity	2.23	0.50	3.22	0.30	2.33	0.38	2.07
Pests and diseases	1.09	1.72	1.44	0.36	2.31	0.45	1.96
Animal welfare	1.54	0.29	2.58	0.80	0.50	2.38	2.17
Labour	0.28	2.40	0.76	2.11	0.11	2.60	1.95
Productivity	4.76	4.33	3.41	2.93	2.36	3.26	2.57
Consumption/processing	2.42	0.25	3.24	1.92	1.83	2.69	2.19
Costs	0.82	1.33	0.76	0.72	0.93	1.73	1.89
Revenue/income	3.82	3.43	3.42	3.24	2.07	3.93	2.33
Collective organisation	1.86	0.20	1.81	1.81	0.90	3.25	1.95
Know-how	0.72	-0.56	0.27	0.45	0.16	2.21	1.85
Overall practice score	29.53	22.04	27.83	16.93	17.17	24.6	-

3.2.4 Representative Board workshop

The Representative Board was asked to identify solutions at the LL scale to alleviate barriers for the implementation of farm scale agroecological practices as discussed during the farmer workshop. The Representative Board judged that the following LL level levers should form the focus of the LL activities:

- Improved water management: water management is a major concern for the representative board members. Improved meteorological information could help manage these scarce resources more efficiently. Moreover, at LL level advice and training on improved water resource management would be beneficial.
- Ensuring improved economic performance of the farm: Strengthening and improving access to different value chains will address many of the concerns of farmers and the Representative Board. In particular it will enable farmers to undertake more value-added processing on farm enhancing revenue and income.

- A lack of know-how to implement improved farming practices: there are a number of farming practices that could be implemented by farmers, but the farmers expressed a need to understand more how these practices should be implemented. It is therefore essential to train and exchange experiences in the field for the different AEPs.

3.2.5 Strategic options for AEPs by farm type

In a joint workshop with all LL leads, the leadership team from each LL identified which AEPs were most suitable for which farm type based on the detailed characterisation of the farm types and the results of the territorial diagnosis, and farmer and Representative Board workshops (Table 8).

The majority of farm level AEPs were suitable for all farm types, specifically: composting, improved irrigation systems, natural pesticides, prickly pear wind breaks and value-added processing. However, while these farm-level AEPs were suitable for all farm types it was noted that the training on their implementation (the LL level AEP) should be adapted for each farm type. For example, the compost mix will be different for the majority of farm types with some farm types integrating significant amounts of animal manure (livestock and diversified farm types) and others not (date palm and arboriculture, and market gardening farm types); natural pesticides will also vary by production focus, as will value-addition processing. The one farm level AEP that was specific to certain farm types was the date pollinator, which was clearly most suited to the farming systems that integrated important amounts of date palms within their production systems.

Table 8: Summary of strategic farm and LL level AEP options by farm type in Laghouat LL

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
Livestock	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Composting (livestock manure management) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved irrigation system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved meteorological information Advice and training at the LL level on improved water resource management
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Natural pesticides 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Value-added processing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthening of value chains to facilitate access to market Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prickly pears (wind breaks) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
Date palms and arboriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Date pollinator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Composting (shredder for date palm pruning residues) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
	and livestock manure management)	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved irrigation system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved meteorological information Advice and training at the LL level on improved water resource management
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Natural pesticides 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prickly pears (wind breaks) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Value-added processing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthening of value chains to facilitate access to market Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
Diversified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Composting (shredder for date palm pruning residues and livestock) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved irrigation system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved meteorological information Advice and training at the LL level on improved water resource management
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prickly pears (wind breaks) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Value-added processing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthening of value chains to facilitate access to market Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Natural pesticides 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Date pollinator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
Market gardening	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Composting (shredder for date palm pruning residues and livestock manure management) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved irrigation system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved meteorological information Advice and training at the LL level on improved water resource management
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prickly pears (wind breaks) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Date pollinator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Value-added processing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthening of value chains to facilitate access to market Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Natural pesticides 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on the use and implementation of farm level AEPs

3.3 Luxor/El Boghdady-EG

3.3.1 Territorial diagnosis

The LL is located in the village of El Boghdady, to the west of Luxor. Climatic conditions and access to irrigation allow farmers to cultivate throughout the year. In the winter, the production focus is on wheat and alfalfa. Sorghum is also grown during this period. Spring and summer are usually dedicated to the cultivation of sugarcane. Farmers employ both traditional and more industrialised methods of farming. Traditional agricultural practices include manual labour with traditional tools, especially in smallholdings. In recent years, most of them started to use more industrialised methods of production, to increase productivity, such as machines, improved seeds, fertilizers, and pesticides. Irrigation is usually via flood irrigation.

3.3.2 Farm types

The main objective for elaborating the typology in this LL is the identification of existing agroecological practices and the promotion of new ones that are better adapted to the area specific conditions. With the assistance of local experts, the main criteria to differentiate the farms were selected: i) farm size, ii) access to water, iii) crop selection, iv) market orientation, v) off-farm income, and vi) soil quality. From these, four farm types were defined (Table 9).

Table 9: Summary of farm types identified in the LL of El Boghdady

Farm type	Description
Commercial farms	Large farms (~1.6 ha) focusing on the production of sugarcane. Wheat and maize cultivated in rotation. Large livestock (cows and buffalo) are also reared. Off-farm income often forms part of the overall livelihood strategy of the household. Highly market oriented with contracted cash crop production. Labour is usually hired. High input intensity, although low amount of phytosanitary inputs. Few sustainable agriculture practices employed.
Livestock oriented	Large livestock producing farms (~1.6 ha), rearing cows, buffalos and monogastrics. Forage crops are cultivated in rotation sorghum followed by wheat; and maize followed by clover. Off-farm income is also common. Labour is hired externally and external inputs are high.
Diversified	Medium sized farms (~0.9 ha) cultivating cereals and forage crops. Monogastric livestock are reared along with poultry. Household labour is used more than hired labour and off-farm income is rare. Production is destined both for market and household consumption. External inputs are less frequently used than the larger farmers.

Farm type	Description
Smallholders	Small subsistence farms (~0.3 ha) cultivating cereals and rearing poultry. Family labour is used and inputs are low (although phytosanitary products are commonly used).

3.3.3 Farmer workshop

3.3.3.1 Agroecological practices

During the Farmer workshop, four farm-level agroecological practices (AEPs) were discussed in detail. These AEPs were selected by the LL leadership based on the insights generated from the territorial diagnosis and conversations with experts. The first task that the farmers were asked to do was to identify the advantages and disadvantages of each of the AEPs. A summary of these discussions is presented in Table 10.

Table 10: Summary of the perceived advantages and disadvantages of different agroecological practices by farmers in the LL of El Boghdady

AEP	Advantages reported by farmers	Disadvantages reported by farmers
Long Rotation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved long-term soil fertility and the productivity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The use of long rotation can cause the need of extra costs to diversify the production meaning new and more inputs such as seeds etc. At the same time there will be a need to have consultancy on the first stages to better understand the synergies of the new system.
Drip Irrigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More efficient use of water. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires financial inputs to add it in the systems. The salts of the soil can be accumulated in the areas of irrigation.
Salinity resistant varieties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can reduce the effects of high salinity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Seed availability. Financial capacity of farmers to acquire seeds.
Raised bed cultivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Raised bed cultivation improves water efficiency and soil fertility Increases soil biodiversity and water holding capacity. Easy to implement and already used by some farmers Does not require new inputs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accumulation of salts in the raised beds. Drying of soil might increase due to greater surface area and increased evapotranspiration.

3.3.3.2 Priority areas of concern

After reviewing the advantages and disadvantages of the AEPs farmers were then asked to rate the importance of a pre-set list of areas of concern to them, which could be expanded based on

discussions with the farmers. Farmers rated each area of concern on a scale of 0-3 generating an importance score.

According to the responses by the farmers (see table 11 for an overview of the importance scores), the five most important areas of concern included:

- Labour requirements
- Biodiversity
- Soil health
- Productivity
- Animal welfare

3.3.3.3 Multi-criteria decision matrix

The final step in the farmer workshop was for the farmers to rate the AEPs as regard their effect on the list of priority areas of concern. The summary of these responses is presented in Table 11.

Two of the AEPs, long rotations and raised bed cultivation, were perceived by the farmers to have trade-offs with labour (ie, increasing labour requirements). Moreover, none of the AEPs were perceived to affect collective organisation and had relatively small effects on animal welfare. On the other hand, the four AEPs all tended to be perceived to have positive effects on water and soil health concerns. Even more strikingly, improved varieties and raised bed cultivation were perceived to have relatively strong positive effects on productivity compared to the long rotation and drip irrigation AEPs. While long rotation and raised bed cultivation were perceived to have negative effects on labour availability, drip irrigation was the only AEP to have an important positive effect on labour availability (decreasing labour requirements). Improved varieties were also perceived to reduce labour requirements, but to a much lesser extent.

Table 11: Multi-criteria decision matrix presenting the perceived effects of different agroecological practices on different areas of concern in the LL of El Boghdady

Area of concern	Improved varieties	Long rotation	Raised bed cultivation	Drip irrigation	Importance Score
Water	1.50	1.56	2.00	2.00	1
Soil	2.50	3.50	2.50	3.50	2
Productivity	4.00	2.13	4.00	1.00	2
Labour	0.75	-0.75	-0.94	2.25	3
Collective organization	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1
Biodiversity	1.50	1.13	0.38	0.00	3
Animal welfare	0.00	0.38	0.50	0.50	2

Area of concern	Improved varieties	Long rotation	Raised bed cultivation	Drip irrigation	Importance Score
Overall practice score	10.25	7.95	8.44	9.25	-

3.3.4 Representative Board workshop

The Representative Board were asked to identify solutions at the LL scale to alleviate barriers for the implementation of farm scale agroecological practices as discussed during the farmer workshop. The most important LL level issues identified by the representative board were water resource management and food productivity. Moreover, the Representative Board judged that the following LL level levers should form the focus of the LL activities:

- Land consolidation: This LL AEP aims to group neighbouring farms. The land consolidation is also a measure that is being promoted by the government. Farmers unify the farms, and this assists in the mechanization of land and better efficiency of inputs application.
- Develop water associations: This LL AEP aims to create a common association of farmers sharing water resources. Water associations are usually managed by the Ministry of Irrigation, although currently few water associations exist. Water associations are responsible for cleaning and maintaining the channels that supply the farms with water. Through the association, farmers can also access in-kind subsidies and participate in initiatives.
- Training and information: In order for the farm level AEPs to be scaled further, it is important for more training and information campaigns to take place. While some farmers already practice a number of the farm level AEPs, overall there is a reticence of some farmers to experiment with these techniques without learning more about the techniques and how to implement them.

3.3.5 Strategic options for AEPs by farm type

In a joint workshop with all LL leads, the leadership team from each LL identified which AEPs were most suitable for which farm type based on the detailed characterisation of the farm types and the results of the territorial diagnosis, and farmer and Representative Board workshops (Table 12).

Each of the four AEPs was found to be suited for the Diversified and Smallholder farm types. All but the long rotation AEP were found to be suitable for the commercial farm types. This is because it would be unlikely for the commercial farms to diversify away from their main cash crop sugarcane. As such, other AEPs appear to be more suitable for these farm types. Due to their production orientation, neither raised bed cultivation nor long rotation were deemed to be suitable for livestock oriented farms.

However, drip irrigation (for forage crops) and salinity resistant forage crops were likely to be important entry points for more sustainable farming for these farm types.

The development of water associations are important LL level AEPs which will facilitate the use of more water efficient irrigation technologies such as drip irrigation. These water associations can facilitate access for, especially, smaller scale farmers to in-kind subsidies. While larger commercial farm types may not need the water associations to access credit for improved irrigation infrastructure, they will still prove important LL level AEPs to improve the management of water resources, ensuring the sustainability of supply.

The remaining three farm level AEPs will require support in the form of training and information in order to scale these practices among farmers. While a number of farmers already use these practices, training and farmer-to-farmer exchanges would help provide concrete advice and evidence to encourage the uptake of these practices. It is important to point out that the application of these technologies and techniques are likely to vary considerably from farm type to farm type. For example the application of long rotations may vary in terms of crops and varieties depending on the farm type. Moreover, raised bed cultivation may be applied differently by commercial farmers compared to smallholders due to differences in access to equipment and labour. As such trainings and information should be adapted to these different farm types.

Table 12: Summary of strategic farm and LL level AEP options by farm type in El Boghdady LL

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
Commercial farms	• Drip irrigation (wheat, maize, and sugarcane)	• Development of water associations
	• Salinity resistant varieties	• Land consolidation • Training and information
	• Raised bed cultivation (not in combination with drip irrigation)	• Land consolidation • Training and information
Livestock oriented	• Drip irrigation (forage crops)	• Development of water associations
	• Salinity resistant varieties	• Land consolidation • Training and information
Diversified	• Long rotation	• Land consolidation • Training and information
	• Drip irrigation (different crop types)	• Development of water associations
	• Salinity resistant varieties	• Land consolidation • Training and information
	• Raised bed cultivation (not in combination with drip irrigation)	• Land consolidation • Training and information

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
Smallholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long rotation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land consolidation • Training and information
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drip irrigation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of water associations
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Salinity resistant varieties 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land consolidation • Training and information
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raised bed cultivation (not in combination with drip irrigation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land consolidation • Training and information

3.4 PK-17-MR

3.4.1 Territorial diagnosis

The LL is located in the commune of Riyadh to the south of the capital city of Nouakchott. It is a peri-urban LL. Census figures from 2013 indicated that the population of Riyadh was 117,030, however, it is now estimated that the population has increased to around 250,000. Agricultural production in Riyadh has been highly influenced by the governmental PK-17 market garden project, which saw the government relocate farmers from other areas around Nouakchott to Riyadh (PK-17) which was largely unpopulated and little-used at that time but had access to water sources. As part of this project the government promoted market gardening, and especially the production of tomatoes and turnips. The government provided agricultural inputs for the farmers.

The rain season lasts from July to February, although it is heaviest from August to September. September is the month with the highest average temperature (29.4°C) and the highest rainfall (19 mm on average). Rainfall is insufficient and too unpredictable for rain-fed agriculture. Irrigation water is sourced from the municipal water board that extracts water from the Senegal river some 200 km away, or from artisanal ground water wells.

The majority of crops grown in the area are market garden crops (tomatoes, turnips, aubergines, mint, okra, lettuce, green onions etc.), which are the main diet and staple food of the Mauritanian population. Agroecological practices common in the LL include:

- Mixed farming approaches
- Manual soil preparation tools (minimum tillage)
- Local seed and nurseries
- Organic fertilisers
- Natural phytosanitary treatments
- Manual irrigation
- Crop rotation
- Agroforestry

3.4.2 Farm types

The selection of the criteria for defining the farm types was based on expert knowledge and opinions. The selected criteria used were: i) land size, ii) self-consumption, and iii) irrigation sources and irrigation technology. Three farm types were identified which are differentiated in terms of land size, profitability, market orientation, and irrigation sources and irrigation practices (Table 13)

Table 13: Summary of farm types identified in the LL of PK-17

Farm type	Description
Military retirees	Constituting 15% of farms in the LL, they cultivate a variety of vegetables on a small plot of land (0.06 ha). Production is for self-consumption and the local market. Households receive income from state military pensions. Farms use both family and wage labour. Low external inputs.
Regional project beneficiaries	Small farms (0.07 ha) constituting around 25% of farms of the LL. Production focus is on vegetables and small livestock, including goats and sheep. Production is destined for market as well as self-consumption. Family labour, but high levels of external inputs are used. No off-farm income.
Illegal market gardeners	The most common farm type (60%) varying in size from 0.04-1.00 ha. Vegetable and fruits are cultivated alongside small livestock (goats and sheep). Production is for both home consumption and market. Input intensity is low.

3.4.3 Farmer workshop

3.4.3.1 Agroecological practices

During the Farmer workshop, seven farm-level AEPs were discussed in detail. These AEPs were selected by the LL leadership based on the insights generated from the territorial diagnosis and conversations with experts. The first task that the farmers were asked to do was to identify the advantages and disadvantages of each of the AEPs. A summary of these discussions is presented in Table 14.

Table 14: Summary of the perceived advantages and disadvantages of different agroecological practices by farmers in the LL of PK-17

AEP	Advantages reported by farmers	Disadvantages reported by farmers
Associated vegetable cropping	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil fertility • Diversification of income and yields. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to water and its management
Organic fertilization and compost	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil fertility • Yields 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to water and its management • Cost of investments
Manual organic fertigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil fertility • Yields • Labour saving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More labour intensive than drip irrigation
Drip irrigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water savings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost of investments

AEP	Advantages reported by farmers	Disadvantages reported by farmers
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yields • Labour saving 	
Improved crop rotations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil fertility • Diversification of income and yields. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to water and its management, cost of investments
Agroforestry and wind-breaks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved yields 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to water and its management • Cost of investments
Organic pesticides	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil fertility • Improved yields 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost of investments

3.4.3.2 Priority areas of concern

After reviewing the advantages and disadvantages of the AEPs, farmers were asked to rate the importance of a pre-set list of areas of concern, which could be expanded based on discussions with the farmers. Farmers rated each area of concern on a scale of 0-3 generating an importance score.

According to the responses by the farmers (see table 15 for an overview of the importance scores), the most important areas of concern included:

- Water – water resources are becoming increasingly scarce coupled with land use change and changes in demographics
- Soil – soil fertility remains problematic leading to lower yields
- Productivity – productivity is a core concern of farmers. Yields should be increased
- Labour – access to labour is restricted as many farms are reliant on family labour. For those farms that use wage labour, the cost is restrictive

3.4.3.3 Multi-criteria decision matrix

The final step in the farmer workshop was for the farmers to rate the AEPs as regard their effect on the list of priority areas of concern. The summary of these responses are presented in Table 15.

Polyculture, rotations, and organic pesticides were rated by farmers to very positively overall, and in particular in relation to the concerns of water and soil health. Agroforestry/wind breaks, organic inputs, and manual weeding were also rated very positively in relation to soil health. Rotations, organic pesticides, and manual fertigation were rated highest with regard to pests and diseases. Manual fertigation was the only AEP that was rated negatively by farmers in relation to labour requirements, it also was received to perform the least positive compared to the other AEPs in relation to biodiversity. On the other hand manual fertigation was perceived to be most positively associated with collective organisation.

Table 15: Multi-criteria decision matrix presenting the perceived effects of different agroecological practices on different areas of concern in the LL of PK-17

Area of concern	Polycultures	Agroforestry/wind break	Rotations	Organic inputs	Compost	Organic pesticides	Manual fertigation	Importance of areas of concern
Water	6.00	3.00	6.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	5.00	3.00
Soil	6.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	6.00	6.00	3.00
Revenue/income	4.70	3.70	2.70	3.70	4.30	4.30	3.70	2.67
Productivity	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	3.00
Pests and diseases	1.70	2.70	5.30	0.70	2.70	5.30	4.70	2.67
Microclimate	2.00	4.00	3.00	2.00	1.00	2.00	1.00	2.33
Labour	4.00	0.00	5.00	3.00	4.00	3.00	-1.00	3.00
Costs	1.50	1.50	1.50	1.50	3.00	1.50	1.50	2.67
Consumption/processing	3.70	0.00	2.70	3.70	2.00	0.00	1.00	2.33
Collective organization	0.70	1.30	0.70	0.70	0.00	2.30	3.00	2.33
Biodiversity	4.00	4.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	1.00	2.33
Animal welfare	3.70	3.30	2.30	0.00	2.00	1.70	0.00	2.67
Overall practice score	40.3	31.3	39.7	32.0	34.7	37.0	29.7	-

3.4.4 Representative Board workshop

During the Representative Board workshop, the most important issues identified were training for water resource management, improving soil quality and pest and disease control, all of which will improve production to meet the needs of the local population. The integration of windbreaks at LL scale, and the organization of producers to enhance product value and the creation of short marketing circuits (cooperatives) were also identified as factors of high importance.

3.4.5 Strategic options for AEPs by farm type

In a joint workshop with all LL leads, the leadership team from each LL identified which AEPs were most suitable for which farm type based on the detailed characterisation of the farm types and the results of the territorial diagnosis, and farmer and Representative Board workshops (Table 16).

Given the broad similarities in production approaches and challenges of the three farm types, the different farm level AEPs were adjudged to be suitable for each of the three farm types. The focus of market gardening of the three farm types was especially suitable for AEPs that diversified production (associated vegetable cropping and improved crop rotations) and enhanced soil and water conservation (organic fertilisation and compost, agroforestry and wind breaks, organic pesticides, and

manual organic fertigation). To stimulate the use of these farm-level AEPs training, workshops and field schools should be implemented to help demonstrate the efficacy of the techniques and contribute to capacity building. In addition, it was thought that it would be useful to undertake soil health testing and water quality monitoring support capacity building and conservation of soil and water resources, especially in relation to the use of organic fertilisation and compost, and manual organic fertilisation. Another overarching LL-level AEP that was thought to be important in stimulating the farm level AEPs was the establishment of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market.

Table 16: Summary of strategic farm and LL level AEP options by farm type in PK-17 LL

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
Military retirees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Associated vegetable cropping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training, workshops and field schools on organizing producers to add value to their products. Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organic fertilization and compost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training, workshops and field schools on composting and the use of manure. Soil health testing Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved crop rotations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training, workshops and field schools on crop rotations. Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agroforestry and wind-breaks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training, workshops and field schools on agroforestry and wind-breaks Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organic pesticides 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training, workshops and field schools on the use of biopesticides Soil health testing Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manual organic fertigation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training, workshops and field schools on composting and the use of manure; water management; pest and

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
		disease control; the use of biopesticides; organizing producers to add value to their products. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water quality testing and monitoring • Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
Regional project beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Associated vegetable cropping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training, workshops and field schools on organizing producers to add value to their products. • Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic fertilization and compost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training, workshops and field schools on composting and the use of manure. • Soil health testing • Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved crop rotations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training, workshops and field schools on crop rotations. • Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agroforestry and wind-breaks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training, workshops and field schools on agroforestry and wind-breaks • Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic pesticides 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training, workshops and field schools on the use of biopesticides • Soil health testing • Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drip irrigation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training, workshops and field schools on composting and the use of manure; water management; pest and disease control; the use of biopesticides; organizing producers to add value to their products. • Water quality testing and monitoring

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
Illegal market gardeners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Associated vegetable cropping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training, workshops and field schools on organizing producers to add value to their products. • Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic fertilization and compost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training, workshops and field schools on composting and the use of manure. • Soil health testing • Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved crop rotations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training, workshops and field schools on crop rotations. • Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agroforestry and wind-breaks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training, workshops and field schools on agroforestry and wind-breaks • Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic pesticides 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training, workshops and field schools on the use of biopesticides • Soil health testing • Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manual organic fertigation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training, workshops and field schools on composting and the use of manure; water management; pest and disease control; the use of biopesticides; organizing producers to add value to their products. • Water quality testing and monitoring • Development of agroecological cooperatives for restricted market (all crops)

3.5 Siliana-TN

3.5.1 Territorial diagnosis

The governorate of Siliana is located in the north-west of the country, with a total surface area of around 4,642 km². According to the latest statistics from the Institut National de la Statistique, the governorate had a population of 229,000 in 2022, 68% of whom live in rural areas. Arable land covers 431,200 hectares, of which only 18,400 hectares are irrigated. Cereals account for the largest area of land cultivated, followed by arboriculture and fodder crops. Livestock farming is also one of the dominant activities in the region, with small ruminants (sheep and goats) predominating, accounting for 89% of the extensive livestock population. Cattle farming, which is more or less intensive accounts for 8.5% of livestock.

Practices aiming to manage soil health, crop diversification, animal health and the reduction of chemical fertilisers are the agroecological practices most commonly implemented in the LL according to the survey results. Crop rotation, the use of localised irrigation to save and manage irrigation water, direct seeding and organic fertilisation through the use of manure were identified as essential practices, highlighting their importance in maintaining soil health and preventing plant-specific diseases.

Although certain obstacles have been identified in the region, the levers for agroecological transition in Siliana are the introduction and wider diffusion of more sustainable practices such as crop rotation, organic fertilisation and the use of localised irrigation (drip irrigation). To change or update traditionally established practices, it is essential to focus on soil resource management, erosion control, veterinary care and farmer training.

The absence of a water source on the farm can be a major obstacle, limiting the diversity of possible crops, particularly those that require water. Farming households also lack financial resources that may not only hinder crop diversification, but also limit the possibility of implementing recycling practices on farm. There is a perceived lack of know-how that could present an obstacle, particularly in the recycling sector, where specific skills are required.

The role of the living lab will be decisive in the future in terms of creating pilot plots, training farmers and helping them to overcome the obstacles associated with a lack of knowledge and perceived values. Some of the people questioned expressed a positive knowledge and opinion of agroecology, which represents a promising opportunity for the agroecological transition in Siliana.

3.5.2 Farm types

The selection of the criteria for defining the farm types was based on existing datasets and expert knowledge and opinions. The three main criteria taken into consideration were: farm size, presence or absence of trees and presence or absence of livestock. It was proposed to consider irrigation as well but farmers growing irrigated cereals are a minority in the region and could not represent a separate representative household. According to the above-mentioned criteria, six farm types were identified: i) Farms smaller than 5 ha with cereals in monoculture and livestock, ii) Farms smaller than 5 ha with cereals, trees and livestock, iii) Farms between 5 ha and 20 ha with cereals in monoculture iv) Farms between 5 ha and 20 ha with cereals, trees and livestock, v) Farms larger than 20 ha with cereals, trees and livestock and vi) Farms larger than 20 ha with cereals and trees (Table 17).

Table 17: Summary of farm types identified in the LL of Siliana

Farm type	Description
Small-scale cereals in monoculture	Farms with less than 5 ha of land that cultivate cereals as a monocrop (durum wheat and barley). Livestock is reared. Households do not engage in off-farm income and consume significant amounts of production. They are less market oriented than the other farm types. The labour required is mainly domestic, with temporary labour employed during the threshing season. External inputs are high. Profitability is low.
Small-scale cereals with trees	Farms with less than 5 ha of land that cultivate cereals in association with olive trees. Livestock is reared. Households do not engage in off-farm income and consume significant amounts of production. They are less market oriented than the other farm types. The labour involved is essentially family-based, with occasional recourse to non-regular labour during the threshing and olive-picking seasons. External inputs are high. Profitability is low.
Medium-scale cereals in monoculture	Farms with between 5-20 ha of land. Cereals are cultivated in monocultures. Household members engage in off-farm activities. Wage labour is hired and external inputs are high. While production is consumed by the household, they also sell a significant amount to market. A large proportion of farmers are engaged in “sustainable agriculture” practices.
Medium-scale cereals with trees	Farms with between 5-20 ha of land. Cereals and olives are cultivated alongside sheep, cattle and poultry. Household members engage in off-farm activities. Wage labour is hired and external inputs are high. While production is consumed by the household, they also sell a significant amount to market. A large proportion of farmers are engaged in “sustainable agriculture” practices.
Large-scale cereals without livestock	The joint biggest farms with more than 20 ha of land, but no livestock. Cereals, legumes, and olives are cultivated. Household members engage in off-farm activities. Wage labour is used and external inputs are high. Profitability is high and households are market oriented. Around half of farms are using “sustainable agriculture” practices.
Large-scale cereals with livestock	The joint biggest farms with more than 20 ha of land, with livestock integration. Cereals, legumes, and olives are cultivated. Household members engage in off-farm activities. Wage labour is used and external inputs are high. Profitability is

Farm type	Description
	high and households are market oriented. Around half of farms use “sustainable agriculture” practices.

3.5.3 Farmer workshop

3.5.3.1 Agroecological practices

In the framework of the farmer workshop in El Krib region, 15 farmers evaluated five agroecological practices selected by the LL leadership based on the insights generated from the territorial diagnosis and conversations with experts. Farmers were asked to identify the advantages and disadvantages of each of the AEPs. A summary of these discussions is presented in Table 18.

Table 18: Summary of the perceived advantages and disadvantages of different agroecological practices by farmers in the LL of Siliana

AEP	Advantages reported by farmers	Disadvantages reported by farmers
No-till sowing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water conservation • Valorization of late rains • Soil fertility and quality conservation • Limit soil erosion • Microbiome conservation (Soil) • Reduced cost at culture implementation • Productivity during the year 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Herbicide use • Low adaptation with livestock activities • Costs of mechanization • Lower yields than conventional farming during optimal growing seasons • Current lack of know-how/knowledge
Crop rotation (with legumes)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conserving water in the soil • Improving soil quality • Weeds control • Disease control • Income enhancing/ income diversification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of water resources • Non-adapted species to the climate • Heterogenous seeds • Market limitation • Lack of knowledge/assistance and support
Fodder species mix	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil fertility improvement • Balanced feeds/ Improve feed quality • Income increased 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of seeds • Marketing limitation and uncertainty (mainly in regard to consumer acceptability) • Current lack of knowledge
Intercropping	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water conservation • Soil fertility Improvement • Weeds control • Beneficial insects • Income diversification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competition between crops for water • More disease • More labour • Lack of knowledge
Controlled grazing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil fertility Improvement • Water conservation • Beneficial insects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less forage • More labour

3.5.3.2 Priority areas of concern

Farmers then rated their most important areas of concern according to a pre-set list. Farmers rated each area of concern on a scale of 0-3 generating an importance score. According to the responses by the farmers (see table 19 for an overview of the importance scores), water, soil health and animal welfare were considered as the most important areas of concern, followed by collective organisation and pests and diseases. Other areas of concern, including micro-climate and biodiversity are also relevant to farmers but with lower priority according to scores mentioned in table 19.

3.5.3.3 Multi-criteria decision matrix

The final step in the farmer workshop was for the farmers to rate the AEPs as regard their effect on the list of priority areas of concern. The summary of these responses are presented in Table 19.

Controlled grazing was perceived to be the only AEP to display a negative impact on an area of concern for the farmers – a perceived negative impact on water resources. Otherwise the AEP was perceived to contribute strongly to soil health, economic profitability and animal welfare. All AEPs were perceived to have a strong positive effect on economic profitability. While fodder associations were deemed to have a relatively less positive impact on water resources and soil health, it scored highly in relation to biodiversity and animal welfare. No till sowing, crop rotations, and inter-cropping were all perceived to be positively correlated with water resources, soil health and economic profitability.

Table 19: Multi-criteria decision matrix presenting the perceived effects of different agroecological practices on different areas of concern in the LL of Siliana

Area of concern	No-till sowing	Crop rotation	Controlled grazing	Fodder association	Intercropping	Importance of areas of concern
Water	5.50	4.09	-4.00	2.50	4.75	2.53
Soil health	4.33	5.00	4.08	2.33	4.75	2.58
Pests and diseases	2.17	2.67	0.58	2.67	1.58	2.14
Microclimate	3.33	2.33	2.75	2.50	3.50	2.07
Economic profitability	4.75	5.17	5.25	5.17	5.42	1.96
Collective organization	2.92	2.08	2.33	1.67	1.25	2.17
Biodiversity	3.92	3.17	2.42	3.67	3.08	1.95
Animal welfare	2.83	3.33	4.00	4.08	2.33	2.57
Overall practice score	29.75	27.84	17.41	24.59	26.66	-

3.5.4 Representative Board workshop

The workshop aimed to identify solutions (at LL scale) to alleviate barriers for AEPs implementation at farm level. Based on the previous workshops, it was decided to discuss marketing limitations and lack of knowledge as the two common barriers for all AEPs.

Regarding marketing limitation, various solutions were proposed: the implementation of storage and packing infrastructure, the involvement of support organizations, the identification of new value chains and the implementation of workshops and training to i) deepen farmers knowledge about the adequate choice of crops and farming systems, and ii) convince consumers of the high nutritional, healthy and economic value of the new cultivated crops, with a view to involving them in a diet transition that is linked to the transition in agricultural practices. Creating startups specialized in labelling less-commercialized products was also discussed as a solution to address the issue of marketing limitations.

Concerning the lack of knowledge of some AEPs, different solutions emerged. Participants agreed that the government should play a role in alleviating this barrier through the encouragement of continuous training in AE. This action will be implemented through supervision, assistance, guidance, grants, etc. At LL scale, farmer empowerment was suggested as a global strategy that can be implemented through different options such as: technical guides, regular field schools and farm visit and awareness campaigns through social media.

3.5.5 Strategic options for AEPs by farm type

In a joint workshop with all LL leads, the leadership team from each LL identified which AEPs were most suitable for which farm type based on the detailed characterisation of the farm types and the results of the territorial diagnosis, and farmer and Representative Board workshops (Table 20).

Different farm level AEPs were deemed to be suitable for the farm types dependent on their production focus. For example, for those with significant livestock integration (eg, small-scale cereals with trees, medium-scale farmers, and large-scale with livestock), controlled grazing and improved fodder species mixes were deemed to be important AEPs. For those farm types that practiced mainly monoculture approaches to crop production (small scale cereals in monoculture and medium scale cereals in monoculture), crop rotations were earmarked as important AEPs, while intercropping AEP was also identified to be suitable for more mixed farming approaches (eg, small scale with tree, medium scale with trees, and large-scale farms). Due to its potential to apply in most contexts of the LL, no till sowing was thought to be suitable for all farm types.

The LL level levers to facilitate the scaling of the farm level AEPs largely depended on the farm type size. In particular it was deemed that the development of a cooperative would facilitate the access to common infrastructure for small and medium scale farms for farm-level AEPs such as no-till sowing. These cooperatives could also be used to facilitate the development of new value chains to stimulate the production of less commercialised crops such as legumes. On the other hand, given their higher financial resources it was expected that larger scale farms would be able to invest in new technologies, but new marketing opportunities through labelling companies or other value chain activities were most likely stimulate the use of farm level AEPs identified. Workshops and trainings were identified as important levers for the uptake of most farm level AEPs and for all farm types. However, these training and workshops should be adapted for each farm type due to differences in resources and production focus.

Table 20: Summary of strategic farm and LL level AEP options by farm type in the LL of Siliana

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
Small-scale cereals in monoculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No-till sowing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop on no-till sowing techniques and advantages (practical sessions will be included) Development of farmer cooperative to facilitate access to common infrastructure and equipment (eg, no-till sower)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crop rotation with legumes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop on crop rotation and inter-cropping as AE practices: advantages, objectives and techniques. Training on short food supply chain for legumes crops Development of farmers' cooperative for marketing of AE products
Small-scale cereals with trees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No-till sowing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on short food supply chain for crops other than cereals Development of farmer cooperative to facilitate access to common infrastructure and equipment (eg, no-till sower)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crop rotation with legumes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop on crop rotation and inter-cropping as AE practices: advantages, objectives and techniques. Training on short food supply chain for legumes crops Development of farmers' cooperative for marketing of AE products

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inter-cropping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop on crop rotation and inter-cropping principles, advantages and impacts on soil fertility Development of farmers' cooperative for marketing of AE products
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Controlled grazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop on fodder species mixtures: benefits for livestock and soil fertility Training on controlled grazing
Medium-scale cereals in monoculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No-till sowing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop on no-till sowing techniques and advantages (practical sessions will be included) Development of farmer cooperative to facilitate access to common infrastructure and equipment (eg, no-till sower)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crop rotation with legumes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop on crop rotation and inter-cropping as AE practices: advantages, objectives and techniques. Training on short food supply chain for legumes crops Development of farmers' cooperative for marketing of AE products
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fodder species mix 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop on fodder species mixtures: benefits for livestock and soil fertility Training on short food supply chain for fodder crops
Medium-scale cereals with trees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No-till sowing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop on no-till sowing techniques and advantages (practical sessions will be included) Development of farmer cooperative to facilitate access to common infrastructure and equipment (eg, no-till sower)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crop rotation with legumes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop on crop rotation and inter-cropping as AE practices: advantages, objectives and techniques. Training on short food supply chain for legumes crops Development of farmers' cooperative for marketing of AE products
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fodder species mix 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop on fodder species mixtures: benefits for livestock and soil fertility Training on short food supply chain for fodder crops

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inter-cropping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop on crop rotation and inter-cropping principles, advantages and impacts on soil fertility • Development of farmers' cooperative for marketing of AE products
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Controlled grazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop on fodder species mixtures: benefits for livestock and soil fertility • Training on controlled grazing
Large-scale cereals without livestock	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No-till sowing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop on no-till sowing techniques and advantages (practical sessions will be included)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop rotation with legumes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating startups specialized in marketing less-commercialized products • Workshop on crop rotation and inter-cropping as AE practices: advantages, objectives and techniques.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inter-cropping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop on crop rotation and inter-cropping principles, advantages and impacts on soil fertility • Creating startups specialized in marketing less-commercialized products
Large-scale cereals with livestock	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop rotation with legumes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating startups specialized in marketing less-commercialized products • Workshop on crop rotation and inter-cropping as AE practices: advantages, objectives and techniques.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inter-cropping 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop on crop rotation and inter-cropping principles, advantages and impacts on soil fertility • Creating startups specialized in marketing less-commercialized products
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No till 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop on no-till sowing techniques and advantages (practical sessions will be included)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fodder species mix 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshop on fodder species mixtures: benefits for livestock and soil fertility
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Controlled grazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training on controlled grazing

3.6 Skoura M'Daz-MA

3.6.1 Territorial diagnosis

The municipality of Skoura M'Daz is located in the Fes-Meknes region and is part of the Boulmane province. It is located between 1000 and 2500 meters above sea level. The municipality is bounded on the north by Tadrej municipality, on the south by Guigou municipality, on the east by El-Mers municipality, and on the west by Tazouta municipality. The municipality's main town is located in the Middle Atlas foothills, 150 km from the provincial headquarters, 64 km from Sefrou, and 90 km from Ifrane, two other main towns in the region.

It has typical arid climate. The majority of precipitation usually falls between November and March, during the winter and spring months. Precipitation in Skoura M'Daz generally falls as rain but sometimes also snow. Snowfall can be heavy in the nearby mountains. The summer months are hot and dry. The annual rainfall for the year 2021-2022 varied between 250mm and 300mm.

The dominant agricultural production systems are arboriculture where olive trees predominate and also include the cultivation of almonds, carob, figs, apple, cherry, plum, vine, pear. Cereal production is also common (barley, durum and soft wheat). Livestock production generally focuses on sheep and goat for both own consumption and for sale to market as a source of income.

3.6.2 Farm types

Based on expert knowledge and opinions the main criteria for defining the local farm households were: i) crop orientation, ii) land fragmentation, iii) self-consumption, and iv) climate change impact. Based on these criteria, three farm types were formulated which show distinct characteristics and challenges (Table 21).

Table 21: Summary of farm types identified in the LL of Skoura-M'Daz

Farm type	Description
Small subsistence	Consists of small-scale, intercropped cereal-vegetables and olive trees near village centres, averaging 0.7 ha and livestock for self-consumption. This farm relies on old irrigation techniques from springs and produces barely enough for self-sufficiency, with onions as the sole cash crop. Leading farmers seek additional income through other agricultural jobs.
Medium mixed livelihoods	Features medium-scale, market-oriented olive farms spanning 2.6 ha, irrigated by the Guigou river, though recent infrastructure damage has hampered water supply and productivity. Farmers here often have off-farm income, and employ mostly hired labour for olive harvesting.

Farm type	Description
Large market oriented	Comprises large-scale mixed cereal-arboriculture, averaging 5.6 ha in mountainous regions, relying on rainfed crops and extensive livestock ranching. These farms are market-focused, heavily dependent on hired labour, and managed by the oldest farmers who face family emigration due to harsh weather conditions.

3.6.3 Farmer workshop

3.6.3.1 Agroecological practices

Building on the findings of the initial territorial diagnosis and discussions with experts, five AE practices were selected by the LL leadership to be discussed at the Farmer workshop, 1) the association of olive trees and aromatic and medicinal plants, 2) surface irrigation and improvement options, 3) drip irrigation, 4) use of manure, and the 5) use of shredded tree pruning residues. Farmers were asked to identify the advantages and disadvantages of each of the AEPs. A summary of these discussions are presented in Table 22.

Table 22: Summary of the perceived advantages and disadvantages of different agroecological practices by farmers in the LL of Skoura M'Daz

AEP	Advantages reported by farmers	Disadvantages reported by farmers
Association of olive trees and medicinal and aromatic plants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversification income, the multiple uses of MAPs (such as for the production of honey and medical products), Positive impact MAP can play against pests and diseases in olive trees through the repellent characteristics of some MAP Potential to be used for the production of plant protection treatments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land use conflict when cultivating MAP in olive orchards that are otherwise used for grazing Costs for seeds and planting material, which were considered to be high, and additional fertilization requirements Increased water requirements, even though, the association was also assessed to help conserve soil moisture In case of continued droughts, potential negative impact on the productivity of olive trees
Surface irrigation and improvement options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water storage may increase the flexibility of farmers to irrigate more efficiently 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased development of weeds, pests and diseases Maintenance is highly labour intensive Soil erosion Water storage too costly (although cheaper than drip irrigation) Land use rights may hinder the construction of reservoirs
Drip irrigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced labour requirements Lower development of weeds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High investment costs for water storage and irrigation equipment High maintenance and energy costs

AEP	Advantages reported by farmers	Disadvantages reported by farmers
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance crop productivity Soil quality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better adapted for small crops such as MAP, and less so for tree crops showing higher water demands
Use of manure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved productivity Longer lasting increase in soil fertility compared to the use of mineral fertilizers Increase in the quality of soil, seen in an increased ease of tillage, a preservation of soil moisture, and a more balanced microclimate close to the soil (e.g. increase soil temperature). Improved biodiversity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manure availability limited Additional cost if manure needs to be bought Good quality manure needs appropriate management to avoid <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased weed abundance Crop damage
Use of shredded tree pruning residues organic amendment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Preservation of soil moisture Lower irrigation demand Lower contribution to the development of weeds (less weed seeds than manure) and pests. Increase crop productivity and crop quality Less costly compared to mineral fertilizers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Higher labour demand Cost for equipment - shredder Loss of firewood and fodder source Only suitable for certain crops

3.6.3.2 Priority areas of concern

Farmers then rated their most important areas of concern according to a pre-set list. Farmers rated each area of concern on a scale of 0-3 generating an importance score. According to the responses by the farmers (see table 23 for an overview of the importance scores). Overall, farmers rated water, productivity, soil health, pests and diseases, and costs as the top five most important areas of concern. Less prominent areas of concern were biodiversity, animal welfare and microclimate.

3.6.3.3 Multi-criteria decision matrix

The final step in the farmer workshop was for the farmers to rate the AEPs as regard their effect on the list of priority areas of concern. The summary of these responses is presented in Table 23.

The use of surface irrigation and manure inputs were perceived by the farmers to be negatively correlated with the most areas of concern. Surface irrigation was perceived to negatively affect water resources, soil health, and pests and diseases, and was expected to increase labour requirements on farm. Manure inputs on the other hand were perceived to negatively affect water resources, and pests and diseases, as well as being a costly and labour intensive AEP. All of the proposed AEPs were deemed to be more expensive than current practices, except for surface irrigation. Labour

requirements were also deemed an important area of concern for all AEPs except for drip irrigation where farmers saw opportunities for enhancing labour resource efficiency. Drip irrigation scored highly on most of the areas of concern compared to the other AEPs, especially as regards water resources, soil health, pests and diseases, labour, productivity, consumption and processing, and revenue and income. Association of MAPs and olives and the use of pruning residues for mulching generally scored somewhere between the upper and lower scores for each of the areas of concern.

Table 23: Multi-criteria decision matrix presenting the perceived effects of different agroecological practices on different areas of concern in the LL of Skoura M'Daz

Area of concern	Association of MAPs/olives	Surface irrigation	Drip irrigation	Manure	Use of pruning residues (mulching)	Importance weights of areas of concern
Water	-2,47	-5,82	5,82	-2,65	1,76	3.00
Soil	1,71	-3,35	5,12	5,47	3,94	2.82
Microclimate	0,76	0,82	1,65	-0,18	3,18	2.12
Biodiversity	0,41	0,82	-0,76	1,29	0,53	2.12
Pests and diseases	2,59	-4,53	3,88	-2,82	2,41	2.76
Animal welfare	1,12	0,53	-0,53	0,59	0,18	2.12
Labour	-2,35	-2,53	3,12	-2,71	-2,88	2.29
Productivity	5,06	0,59	4,12	5,18	3,82	2.94
Consumption/processing	3,35	1,35	2,94	2,88	2,06	2.35
Costs	-2,76	-0,24	-1,94	-2,76	-3,00	2.65
Revenue/income	3,76	1,76	4,13	4,00	2,35	2.59
Overall practice score	11,18	-10,59	25,76	8,29	14,35	

3.6.4 Representative Board workshop

The Representative Board was asked to brainstorm solutions for the challenges identified by farmers in previous workshop regarding the implementation of farm scale agroecological practices. Participants collectively explored options to address these issues at Living Lab (LL) level. Options discussed included training and collective organization for managing water and organic matter resources, for commercializing olive oil and MAPs as a 'package', and for financing necessary infrastructure and equipment.

Options included:

Water management - Utilize crops that can adapt to limited water resources (e.g. quinoa); better maintenance of the infrastructure of water channels by professional water management organization;

options to finance transition to drip irrigation; need to address the issue of land registration¹ as a prerequisite for drip irrigation subsidies).

Marketing of MAP and olives as a package - Processing the products together (producing aromatized olive oil); training on transformation, ensure availability of equipment and work on quality assurance, develop relations between customers and producers working with the potential of social media and diversify the customer base; implement labelling.

Enhance the utilization of organic fertilizers, such as shredded tree pruning residues and manure (which is often lacking in quantity and of low quality contributing to weed pressure) - Ensure availability of equipment (e.g., shredders); raise awareness among farmers about the importance of using organic fertilizers and provide training on how to produce and effectively use them (e.g., training on composting of manure to reduce weed seed infestation; establish a professional agricultural organization responsible for processing organic matter sources such as manure and tree pruning residues, to organic fertilizers.

3.6.5 Strategic options for AEPs by farm type

In a joint workshop with all LL leads, the leadership team from each LL identified which AEPs were most suitable for which farm type based on the detailed characterisation of the farm types and the results of the territorial diagnosis, and farmer and Representative Board workshops (Table 24).

Given the similarities in the production systems, all five farm level AEPs were deemed suitable for the three farm types. However, LL level AEPs aimed at stimulating the uptake of the farm level AEPs differed by farm type. Specifically, given the lower income and access to financial resources, small subsistence and medium mixed livelihood farm types require support for common processing and marketing of agricultural products and the purchase, rental, or use of common or private infrastructure (eg, shredders, irrigation infrastructure). These could be provided by the creation of professional organisations such as cooperatives. Another important LL level AEP for these farm types was the settlement of property issues (land registration) at the community level. According to the territorial diagnosis, large market orientated farms already tended to have secure land tenure. Training in transformation, quality management and labelling, ONSSA certification (National Food Safety Authority) was identified as an important LL level AEP for large market oriented farms. Training on a different range of topics such as composting, manure management, and water resources management, were identified as important levers for the uptake of most farm level AEPs for all three

¹ Land registration enhances land tenure security by proving individuals and communities with greater security over their land rights and facilitating access to credits to invest in their land

farm types. However, these trainings should be adapted at least to account the significant different between the small and medium farm types compared to the large market oriented farm types.

Table 24: Summary of strategic farm and LL level AEP options by farm type in the LL of Siliana

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
Small subsistence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Association of olive trees and MAPs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Common processing and marketing olive oil and MAP Settlement of property issues (proof of property) at the community level
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved surface irrigation or drip irrigation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on water management Professional organization sourcing equipment (e.g. shredders, irrigation infrastructure) and producing organic fertilizers (e.g. compost)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of manure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on composting of manure and pruning residues Professional organization sourcing equipment (e.g. shredders) and producing organic fertilizers (e.g. compost)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of shredded tree pruning residues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on composting of manure and pruning residues Professional organization sourcing equipment (e.g. shredders) and producing organic fertilizers (e.g. compost)
Medium mixed livelihoods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Association of olive trees and MAPs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Common processing and marketing olive oil and MAP Settlement of property issues (proof of property) at the community level
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved surface irrigation or drip irrigation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on water management Professional organization sourcing equipment (e.g. shredders, irrigation infrastructure) and producing organic fertilizers (e.g. compost)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of manure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on composting of manure and pruning residues Professional organization sourcing equipment (e.g. shredders) and producing organic fertilizers (e.g. compost)

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of shredded tree pruning residues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on composting of manure and pruning residues Professional organization sourcing equipment (e.g. shredders) and producing organic fertilizers (e.g. compost)
Large market oriented	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Association of olive trees and MAPs 	Training in transformation, quality management and labelling, ONSSA certification (National Food Safety Authority)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved surface irrigation or drip irrigation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on water management
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of manure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on composting of manure and pruning residues
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use of shredded tree pruning residues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training on composting of manure and pruning residues

3.7 Tizi Ouzou-DZ

3.7.1 Territorial diagnosis

The area covered by the Living Lab in Tizi-Ouzou (Yakouren and Azazga communes) is mountainous and forested. This has favoured production systems that are essentially agroforestry and agro-pastoral systems. However, the effects of climate change have had an impact on the area's water resources, with a drop in rainfall and snowfall, and an increase in temperature, leading to the drying up of water sources and groundwater which have traditionally enabled farmers to produce a wide range of market garden and tree crops.

The mountainous and forested nature of the area, although favourable to livestock farming (cattle, sheep and goats), limits the area available for cultivation, especially in the municipality of Yakouren. This does not prevent the area from producing olive oil and boasting a wealth of agroecological practices that enable it to cope with these environmental challenges.

Another notable feature of the area is the involvement of women in agricultural and livestock activities, their dynamism through women's organisations give them access to financial support services, training and agricultural advice. In addition, agroecological principles have been adopted to help maintain farming activity despite the difficulties identified and several avenues have been identified to promote agroecological practices and principles in order to remedy the effects of climate change and pollution in the region.

The territorial diagnosis identified a number of existing AEPs practiced by farmers in the LL, including:

- Diversifying, combining and rotating crops.
- Agro-forestry: trees, hedges, reforestation.
- Soil and water management and conservation: mulching, OM burial, troughs, half-moon, contour sowing, stone cordon, grass strips, etc.
- Biological and mechanical control, other alternatives to pesticides: habitat conservation and management, natural pesticides, mechanical weed control.
- Farmers' seeds: massal selection, cultivation and conservation of seeds, exchanges/farmers, new species/varieties.

3.7.2 Farm types

Based on expert knowledge and opinions the main criteria to differentiate the farm types selected were: i) presence of livestock, ii) type of livestock production, iii) type of crop production, and iv) scale of operations. From these variables, six farm types were defined. These are summarized in Table 25.

Table 25: Summary of farm types identified in the LL of Tizi Ouzou

Farm type	Description
Diversified	Small, mixed farms (0-1 ha), with the majority of production consumed at home. Low levels of external inputs and reliant on household labour. Off-farm income constitutes the majority of overall livelihood.
Olive	Medium sized farms (1-3 ha) with a mix of olive orchards and livestock production. Production is for both home consumption and market, although profitability is low. Low levels of external inputs and reliant on household labour. Off-farm income activities constitute a part of their livelihood strategy.
Cereal	Large farms (5-20 ha) with a few small livestock. Mostly market oriented production of cereals and melons. Olive production too. Engages labourers, especially during peak work periods. Medium to high profitability and high use of external inputs (low or no use of organic inputs).
Sheep/goat	Small farms (0-1 ha) with high levels of home vegetable consumption. Production oriented to sheep and goat destined for market from which a significant proportion of overall income is generated (some off-farm income). Labour is mostly household labour. Virtually no use of external inputs.
Dairy cattle	Medium sized farms (1-3 ha) with market oriented cattle dairy production. Medium profitability of farm. Vegetable production consumed by the household. Virtually no use of external inputs.
Medicinal and aromatic plants	Micro farms (0-1 ha) often run by women. MAPs produced for market. Small livestock also reared. Virtually no use of external inputs. Labour comes from the household.

3.7.3 Farmer workshop

3.7.3.1 Agroecological practices

Building on the findings of an initial territorial diagnosis six AEPs were selected by the LL leadership. These AEPs were explored at the farmer workshop aimed at identifying the advantages and disadvantages of AEPs at farm level. A summary of these discussions are presented in Table 26.

Table 26: Summary of the perceived advantages and disadvantages of different agroecological practices by farmers in the LL of Tizi Ouzou.

AEP	Advantages	Disadvantages
Local seeds	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consume less water and supporting drought resistance • Well-adapted to the soil types, which enhances their effectiveness and reduces the need for soil amendments • Resistant to pests and diseases, reducing the reliance on chemical pesticides • several niches for consumption, processing, and preservation, adding value to the agricultural produce 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for careful conservation
Manure use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improves soil structure, texture, and nutrients, making it more fertile, while also helping to store water • Biodiversity increases attracting useful fauna such as earthworms, also helping to enhance germination rates • Higher yields and better crop performance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appearance of weeds • More labour
Liquid manure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increases soil fertility • Productivity and yields 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time requirements • Organisational requirements
Mulching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Saves water by reducing transpiration and retaining moisture in the soil • Lowers soil temperature and enriches the soil with organic matter, thereby enhancing soil health and fertility • Reduces weeding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased humidity under the mulch can promote fungal growth
Agroforestry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve water retention and reduce water loss • Enriches the soil through the composting of dead leaves, which adds organic matter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competition for water between trees and crops, especially if trees are not spaced appropriately

AEP	Advantages	Disadvantages
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduces soil erosion and allows for better use of space, enhancing overall land productivity 	
Crop rotation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improves crop health by reducing diseases and creating an unfavourable environment for pests Increases productivity by maintaining soil fertility and reducing pest pressure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires more labour, skills, and techniques

3.7.3.2 Priority areas of concern

After reviewing the advantages and disadvantages of the AEPs farmers were then asked to rate the importance of a pre-set list of areas of concern to them, which could be expanded based on discussions with the farmers. Farmers rated each area of concern on a scale of 0-3 generating an importance score. The top five areas of concern for the farmers in the workshop were water, biodiversity, animal welfare, soil health, and productivity. The areas of least concern were labour, consumption/processing, and revenue and income. See table 27 for an overview of the importance scores.

3.7.3.3 Multi-criteria decision matrix

The final step in the farmer workshop was for the farmers to rate the AEPs as regard their effect on the list of priority areas of concern. The summary of these responses are presented in Table 27.

Local seeds and liquid manure AEPs were rated by farmers as performing very well on many of the areas of concern, especially water resources, soil health, biodiversity, costs and revenue and income. Mulching tended to be scored less highly than the other AEPs receiving the lowest scores for biodiversity, animal welfare, consumption and processing, revenue and income, and collective organisation. Organic fertilisation was the only AEPs to be rated negatively by farmers on any of the areas of concern, namely pests and diseases, otherwise it scored relatively well on water resources, soil health, costs, and revenue and income. The AEPs of agroforestry and rotations tended to score neither the highest nor the lowest among the AEPs, except for soil health where agroforestry scored the lowest.

Table 27: Multi-criteria decision matrix presenting the perceived effects of different agroecological practices on different areas of concern in the LL of Tizi Ouzou

Area of concern	Local seeds	Organic fertilization	Liquid manure	Mulching	Agroforestry	Rotation	Importance of areas of concern
Water	5.14	4.71	4.38	4.93	3.43	2.77	2.88

Area of concern	Local seeds	Organic fertilization	Liquid manure	Mulching	Agroforestry	Rotation	Importance of areas of concern
Soil	3.50	3.79	4.29	3.15	1.31	3.31	2.35
Microclimate	2.43	1.57	1.08	1.92	3.00	2.14	2.25
Biodiversity	3.50	2.50	2.92	1.21	3.43	2.36	2.65
Pests and diseases	2.71	-1.14	3.00	0.08	0.93	3.31	2.24
Animal welfare	3.15	1.14	1.07	0.92	2.36	3.14	2.47
Labour	2.93	0.86	2.86	1.64	0.64	1.00	1.76
Productivity	3.08	3.15	3.54	3.42	2.85	4.08	2.29
Consumption/processing	3.29	2.64	2.75	1.77	2.57	3.21	2.00
Costs	4.14	3.57	4.29	2.14	1.93	1.71	2.24
Revenue/income	3.07	3.50	3.64	2.43	2.46	3.79	2.12
Collective organization	3.43	2.57	2.07	0.86	2.21	2.71	2.18
Overall practice score	40.37	28.86	35.89	24.47	27.12	33.53	-

3.7.4 Representative Board workshop

The objective of the workshop was to identify solutions (at LL scale) to alleviate barriers for AEPs implementation at farm level. The major obstacles identified by the participants are related to access to agricultural land, water management, and product commercialization. Access to agricultural land is constrained by factors such as private ownership often held by emigrants and challenging geographical conditions. Water management is complicated by a diminishing resource, exacerbated by demographic and climatic pressures. Finally, the commercialization of products is hindered by a lack of adequate structures for sale and distribution, as well as insufficient recognition of local products in the markets.

The agroecological practices at LL level that emerged from the discussions are:

- Exploitation of the new regulations for the use of forest lands
- Creation of cooperatives for the development of value chains
- Structuring local markets to facilitate the flow of products and reduce risks
- Mobilization and collective management of water resources
- Training and capacity building linked to farmer level AEPs

3.7.5 Strategic options for AEPs by farm type

In a joint workshop with all LL leads, the leadership team from each LL identified which AEPs were most suitable for which farm type based on the detailed characterisation of the farm types and the results of the territorial diagnosis, and farmer and Representative Board workshops (Table 28). The

farm level AEPs were reviewed and matched with the different farm types. The AEPs selected for each farm type varied according to the main production focus of the farm type. In addition to the six farm AEPs selected for the farmer and representative board workshops, deficit irrigation was included as an AEP to help address the challenges related to the concern of water.

For the livestock oriented farm types (sheep/goat and dairy cattle) and the olive-focused farmers, the farm AEPs identified related to the enhancing of soil health through organic fertilisation, liquid manure, and mulching, as well as the integration of agroforestry practices. For the farm types with important arable crop production (diversified, cereal, and medicinal and aromatic plant farms), in addition to the AEPs to support soil health, other AEPs identified included the use of local seeds, improved rotations, and deficit irrigation. The integration of agroforestry practices was also identified.

The LL level AEPs that aimed at facilitating the adoption of the farm level AEPs were also identified. In particular it was asserted that farm level AEPs which introduced less commercialised crops or altered existing production systems should be coupled with the development of cooperatives that could help with the marketing and commercialisation of the new products, as well as activities that aimed to structure local markets to facilitate the flow of products and reduce risks. The creation of cooperatives could also help facilitate the use of farm level AEPs by increasing demand and return on investment for certain agricultural products. For the scaling of deficit irrigation, it was deemed necessary to also mobilize the collective management of water resources at the LL level. This would sensitise farmers to the importance and potential of enhanced water use efficiency. For many of the farm level AEPs trainings and capacity building was recommended especially for the use of local seeds, organic fertilisation, liquid manure, mulching, rotations, and deficit irrigation.

Table 28: Summary of strategic farm and LL level AEP options by farm type in the LL of Tizi Ouzou

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
Diversified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organic fertilization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Liquid manure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mulching (with pruning residues) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agroforestry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exploitation of the new regulations for the use of forest lands (MAPs) Creation of cooperatives (MAPs) Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rotation (seasonal vegetables and faba beans) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structuring local markets to facilitate the flow of products and reduce risks.

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of cooperatives (seasonal vegetables) • Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deficit irrigation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobilization and collective management of water resources • Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local seeds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and capacity building
Olive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic fertilization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of cooperatives (olives) • Structuring local markets to facilitate the flow of products and reduce risks.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Liquid manure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mulching (with pruning residues) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deficit irrigation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and capacity building • Mobilization and collective management of water resources
Cereal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local seeds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic fertilization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Liquid manure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mulching (with pruning residues) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agroforestry (olive trees and faba beans) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structuring local markets to facilitate the flow of products and reduce risks. • Creation of cooperatives (olives and legumes)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rotation (faba beans) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structuring local markets to facilitate the flow of products and reduce risks. • Creation of cooperatives (legumes)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deficit irrigation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training and capacity building • Mobilization and collective management of water resources
Sheep/goat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic fertilization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structuring local markets to facilitate the flow of products and reduce risks. • Creation of cooperatives (livestock)

Farm type	Farm level AEP	LL level AEP
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Liquid manure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mulching 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agroforestry (olive trees and faba beans) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structuring local markets to facilitate the flow of products and reduce risks. Creation of cooperatives (olives and legumes)
Dairy cattle	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organic fertilization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structuring local markets to facilitate the flow of products and reduce risks. Creation of cooperatives (dairy)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Liquid manure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mulching 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agroforestry (olive trees and faba beans) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structuring local markets to facilitate the flow of products and reduce risks. Creation of cooperatives (olives and legumes)
Medicinal and aromatic plants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local seeds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Exploitation of the new regulations for the use of forest lands (MAPs) Creation of cooperatives (MAPs) Structuring local markets to facilitate the flow of products and reduce risks. Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organic fertilization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Liquid manure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mulching 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agroforestry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structuring local markets to facilitate the flow of products and reduce risks. Creation of cooperatives (olives and MAPs)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rotation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and capacity building
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deficit irrigation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training and capacity building Mobilization and collective management of water resources

Chapter 4

Discussion & conclusion

4. Discussion & Conclusion

4.1 Commonalities and differences among LLs regarding concerns

From the presentation of results in Chapter 3, it is clear that a number of concerns are common throughout the LLs of the NATAE project. From an environmental perspective, soil degradation (fertility loss) and increasing pressures on the water resources were considered to be important challenges in all of the LLs. It is unsurprising that these environmental challenges are identified by all LLs as of major concern. Land degradation in the Middle East and North African region is indeed occurring at an alarming rate with currently more than a quarter of all arable land now categorised as degraded (World Bank 2019, FAO 2015). Moreover, climate change has led to high year-to-year precipitation variability in North Africa causing severe draughts and heat waves (Schilling et al., 2020, Cook et al., 2016; Lelieveld et al., 2016). These extremes of weather are coupled with an agricultural sector that is by far the largest extractor of water resources, usually accounting for over 80% of all water used in North African countries (Schilling et al., 2012).

In addition to these environmental challenges in the LLs, other common challenges identified included an ever-decreasing labour pool, difficulties generating sufficient income from farming activities, and poor access to markets and opportunities for value addition processing. These challenges are common to farmers located throughout North Africa. The rapid urbanisation of North African countries, where around 70% of the population now live in urban centres compared to only around a quarter of the population a few decades ago, has created a situation where the rural population is increasingly older and fewer young people are available to work on-farm (Walther 2021). The prevalence of rural poverty is one of the drivers for rural out-migration in the region with 60-70% of the region's poor people living in rural areas, and around 40% of rural residents considered poor (FAO and IFAD 2007). This is compounded by the fact that often, especially smaller-scale farmers find it difficult to access markets or participate in the value chain through the processing of farm products.

Another challenge that was identified in a number of the LLs (El Boghdady, PK-17, Skoura-M'Daz and Tizi Ouzou) was related to secure access to agricultural land either due land tenure insecurity or land fragmentation processes. Indeed the majority of farm types in the LLs owned relatively small amounts of land (usually less than 5 ha, but sometimes even less than 1 ha). Such small farm sizes is important as it can reduce the opportunities for farmers to enhance profitability through larger economies of scale. Such challenges of access to land are commonly reported in the Middle East and North Africa where land property rights were often inherited from traditional, colonial and post-colonial agricultural policies. The consequences are often observed in the farming systems where land fragmentation and insecure land tenure leads to lower investments in the land and farm management (Bertini et al. 2021, Caulfield et al. 2020a).

One of the concerns that was less commonly identified by the LL farmers and representative boards was biodiversity loss, although the farmers and representative boards of Tizi Ouzou, Luxor and Siliana were exceptions to this. Notwithstanding this omission in the discussions of the LL, biodiversity loss is a major challenge in North African agricultural dryland systems as found in a number of studies (Zdruli, 2023, Sánchez-Bayo et al., 2021, Zhang & Yunhai Zhang, 2023). This finding is important as it may reveal a common challenge in processes aimed at fostering agroecological transitions, and potentially informs the need to frame dialogues on improved agricultural practices.

One of the main challenges is that the role biodiversity plays in ensuring a productive and sustainable agroecosystem is commonly undervalued. While it is widely accepted in the scientific literature that biodiversity contributes to more productive and sustainable farming (Brooker et al., 2021, Ricciardi et al., 2021, Jiao et al., 2022) it may be that this is less recognised by farmers and broader stakeholders in the local food systems. This contrasts strongly with the importance farmers and other stakeholders place on soil fertility and access to water, which obviously also play critical roles in ensuring sustainable farm productivity. This undervaluing or misunderstanding of the food system services that biodiversity provides may be part of the reason why it is seemingly perceived to be less important than other concerns identified by the LLs. Two implications of this are that: 1) there is a clear need to engage with actors and enhance understanding across the food system of the beneficial role biodiversity plays in creating productive and sustainable agroecosystems; and 2) while there remains a lack of valuation of biodiversity's role in agricultural systems, the framing of the narrative related to agroecological transitions should continue to link to more commonly understood ecosystem benefits, while trying to broaden the understanding around biodiversity and its relation to other food system functions.

4.2 Commonalities and differences among LLs regarding AEPs

Similar to the concerns, LLs identified a number of the same farm-level AEPs, namely: drip irrigation, organic amendments (manure/mulching/shredder), crop rotations and associations, and intercropping or agroforestry. It is not surprising that such farm level AEPs were identified by the majority, if not all of the LLs, given the importance of the common concerns of soil fertility, and access to and management of water resources. As already well recognised in the scientific literature, these AEPs are well known to enhance water use efficiency, increase water retention capacity and soil fertility (chemical, physical, and biological) (Caulfield et al., 2020b; Requier-Desjardins et al., 2024, Arya et al. 2017), decrease pests and diseases, and enhance overall productivity (Caulfield et al., 2020c; Romero Antonio et al., 2024).

In addition to the common farm-level AEPs across LLs, a number of LLs also identified AEPs not otherwise identified by the other LLs. These included: a manual pollinator of date palms, prickly pear wind breaks (Llaghouat), organic pesticides (Llaghouat and PK-17), long-rotations and raised bed cultivation (Luxor), no till practices, controlled grazing (Siliana), and local seeds (Tizi Ouzou). The identification of different AEPs in different LLs is not surprising given that the contexts of each of the LLs is unique, even if located in similar agroecological contexts. The identification of common AEPs in the different LLs is an important observation. It highlights the fact that despite the heterogeneity among the LLs, there is great scope for cross-LL learning. This cross-LL learning is integrated explicitly within the NATAE project with cross-site visits taking place in 2025 and regular workshops communicating the advances and developments in each LL. Moreover, the fact that a number of LL have identified specific farm-level AEPs means that there is a need and demand to adapt AEPs to local contexts. This underlines the importance of the LL approach, where innovations are developed and adapted in order to address local contexts (Cascone et al., 2024; Marselis et al., 2024).

As for the farm-level AEPs, a number of similar LL-level AEPs were also identified by the LLs. Specifically, many of the LLs identified the need for trainings, common infrastructure, the development of cooperatives (for marketing and access to common infrastructure), and mechanisms for trying to enhance land consolidation. These LL-level AEPs will no doubt play an important role in facilitating the scaling of the farm-level AEPs in each of the LLs. Notwithstanding these entry points, it is important to note that little was explicitly identified at the LL-level that addressed the common challenges of a dwindling labour supply and access to finances. While it is likely that some of the LL-level AEPs may be able to address aspects related to these challenges (e.g., the development of cooperatives, common infrastructure), it is likely that practices and innovations above the level of the LL will be necessary to address these challenges and others. This finding underlines the fact that agroecological transitions are always situated in a multi-scale socio-ecological system that require activities at different levels and by many different actors (Tittonell, 2020).

4.3 Methodology reflections – strategic options for agroecological transitions

The methodological process through which LLs identified their strategic options for agroecological transitions (Chapter 2) proved to be particularly useful. The territorial diagnosis was key in providing the contextual background as to what AEPs are currently practiced and the socio-ecological factors that have moulded and continue to mould the agricultural systems of the LLs. The workshops with the Representative Board and the farmers built on this deeper understanding of the context involving the core actors of the local food systems in the identification of the most pressing challenges and potential

solutions of relevance. The development of the farm typologies per LL further enabled the LLs to take a more nuanced approach to understanding which AEPs at both farm and LL levels are suitable for which farm type, in effect creating a (strategic) toolbox of AEPs per farm type.

One of the main challenges encountered in the methodology was in the translation of outputs of the farmer and representative board workshops and linking them to specific farm types. While in some instances this process was straight-forward, it required an in-depth understanding of the production system of each of the farm types. This was facilitated by the territorial diagnosis and the farm type characterisations.

Another important reflection on the methodology was that in some cases it was clear that a number of the farm-level AEPs and many LL-level AEPs were suitable for all the farm types of the LL in question. This in itself is not an issue nor surprising, given that there will be a lot of common challenges and solutions within the same context (Bagagnan et al 2024). However, in order to take the strategic options further it will be necessary to develop the options and pathways to scaling in more detail, highlighting any remaining challenges or opportunities that are not addressed in the strategic options identified. This will make the strategic options even more specific to the farm types of the LLs.

4.4 Next steps

The LL leadership teams have identified the strategic options for agroecological transitions as reviewed in this deliverable. However, these strategic options should now be scaled and operationalised with core activities undertaken within the LLs. Among these core activities will be the cross-site visits, the participatory experimental and demonstration plots in each LL, the integrated modelling chain analysis and the scenario workshops, and the ongoing exploitation and communication activities (D5.6) as part of the NATAE project. In addition, further discussions will also have to take place at the LL level to further map the pathways to scaling of the strategic AEP options. This will include providing further detail on the different AEPs identified at the farm level and their potential to lead to more sustainable farming transitions; as well as engaging more with local and national stakeholders about how to implement the LL-scale AEPs (eg, water management associations, cooperatives, trainings) at a more intense and geographically broader scale. This will link with other work being conducted in WP4 and WP6 which focuses on larger systems analyses, scenarios development, and on national, regional and international policies related to agroecological transition processes in North Africa. This complementary analysis will further strengthen and deepen the understanding of the pathways that can contribute to sustainable agroecological transitions. It is foreseen that this complementary work can be integrated in the upcoming Deliverable 4.8 scheduled for early 2026.

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